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Thesis in the course of studies: Transformation Studies

Eco-Social Policies and Sustainable Welfare:

A systematic literature review of contemporary eco-social policy proposals

Keywords: eco-social policy, sustainable welfare, basic needs, planetary boundaries, social policy, environmental policy, systematic literature review

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Table of Contents

TABLE OF FIGURES	III
TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS	IV
ABSTRACT.....	V
1. INTRODUCTION	1
2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND	5
2.1. THE VISION: SUSTAINABLE WELFARE	5
2.1.1. Compatibility with Planetary Boundaries.....	5
2.1.2. Satisfaction of Basic Needs	9
2.2. THE INSTRUMENT: ECO-SOCIAL POLICIES.....	14
2.2.1. Public Policy	14
2.2.2. Environmental Policy	17
2.2.3. Social Policy	21
2.2.4. Eco-Social Inequality and Risk.....	24
2.2.5. Eco-Social Policy	27
3. METHODOLOGY: SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW	33
3.1. METHODOLOGICAL APPROPRIATENESS	33
3.2. ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA.....	35
3.3. SEARCH STRATEGY	38
3.4. QUALITATIVE CONTENT ANALYSIS.....	40
4. FINDINGS.....	42
4.1. SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS.....	42
4.2. QUALITATIVE SYNTHESIS OF ECO-SOCIAL POLICY PROPOSALS.....	47
4.2.1. Basic Income Policies.....	48
4.2.2. Working Time Policies.....	51
4.2.3. Basic Service Policies.....	53
4.2.4. Wealth and Income Regulation Policies	55
4.2.5. Labor Market Policies	56
5. DISCUSSION	60
5.1. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS	60
5.2. TRANSFORMATIVE POTENTIAL OF ECO-SOCIAL POLICIES.....	61
5.3. CONCEPTUAL ISSUES OF ECO-SOCIAL POLICY.....	65

5.4. Eco-Social Policy Implementation	74
6. Conclusion	80
Bibliography	84
Appendix A: The 2025 Update to the Planetary Boundaries	115
Appendix B: Search String Overview	116
Appendix C: MaxQDA Coding Snippet	121
Appendix D: All Databases.....	122

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Hierarchical Basic Needs Theory; adapted from Doyal and Gough (1991, p. 170).	12
Figure 2: Contrasting Definitional Approaches to Eco-Social Policy; own figure.....	30
Figure 3: Eligibility Criteria; own figure	36
Figure 4: PRISMA Graph; adapted from Gräbner-Radkowsch & Strunk (2023, p. 3)	42
Figure 5: Publication Year; own figure	44
Figure 6: Publication Outlet; own figure	45
Figure 7: Publication Database; own figure.....	46
Figure 8: The House of Eco-Social Policy Proposals; own figure	48
Figure 9: Theory of Change for Eco-Social Policy; own figure	69
Figure 10: Eco-Social Policy Typology; own figure	70
Figure 11: Theory of Change – Universal Basic Income; own figure	71
Figure 12: The 2025 Update to the Planetary Boundaries; reprinted from Stockholm Resilience Center (2025), Licensed under CC BY-NC-ND 3.0	115
Figure 13: MAXQDA Coding Snippet	121

Table of Abbreviations

EW = EcoWelfare Zotero

PI = Participation Income

PRISMA = Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses

SLR = Systematic Literature Review

UBI = Universal Basic Income

UBS = Universal Basic Services

WoS = Web of Science

WTR = Working Time Reduction

Abstract

Humanity is living in a world increasingly out of balance, characterized by escalating ecological crises alongside stagnation or deterioration in the satisfaction of basic human needs. These developments underscore two interrelated imperatives: the need for a social-ecological transformation and the recognition of an eco-social nexus. The research field of eco-social policy and sustainable welfare seeks (a) to advance the vision of satisfying basic human needs within planetary boundaries and (b) to develop policy proposals capable of addressing eco-social challenges and enabling sustainable welfare. Yet, the field still lacks systematic mapping of the eco-social policy proposals that currently structure academic debate. Addressing this gap motivates the aim of this thesis, which is to systematically review contemporary eco-social policy proposals discussed in academic literature published between 2021 and 2025. This aim is pursued through a systematic literature review of peer-reviewed journal publications that explicitly discuss eco-social policy proposals. Applying predefined eligibility criteria reduced an initial pool of 824 publications to a final sample of 23 studies. The findings indicate that contemporary research engages with a diverse range of eco-social policy proposals, albeit with markedly uneven levels of scholarly attention. The “House of Eco-Social Policy Proposals” illustrates this variation by distinguishing between core proposals (universal basic income, working time reduction, and universal basic services), semi-core proposals (participation income, selected income and wealth regulation policies, and labor guarantees), and peripheral proposals (such as eco-social retraining or information policies). Across the literature, social objectives are more often articulated explicitly, whereas ecological objectives tend to be linked more indirectly to policy proposals. By synthesizing existing research and critically examining prevailing definitional approaches to eco-social policy, the thesis contributes to literature in two main ways. First, it clarifies the current direction of scholarly debate and identifies under-researched areas, most notably eco-social labor-market policies. Second, by introducing a theory of change perspective and proposing a typology that distinguishes between strong and weak eco-social policy proposals, the thesis enhances conceptual clarity and supports the further development of the research field.

1. Introduction

Humanity is living in what has been described as a world “*out of balance*”¹ (Fanning & Raworth, 2025), in which progress towards a “safe and just space for humanity” (Raworth, 2017, p. 44) remains insufficient. While modest improvements have been made since the early 2000s in meeting certain dimensions of a social foundation for humanity – the “just space” – recent evidence indicates stagnation or regression in core areas such as undernourishment, youth unemployment, access to safe drinking water, social support, corruption perceptions, food security, and political voice (Fanning & Raworth, 2025, p. 48). At the same time, ecological² thresholds – the “safe operating space for humanity” (Rockström et al., 2009, p. 472) – show no sign of improvement (Appendix A “The 2025 Update to the Planetary Boundaries”): seven of nine planetary boundaries have now been exceeded, and trends point toward further deterioration (Sakschewski et al., 2025).

These developments highlight two fundamental points. First, profound *social-ecological transformation* – a “Great Transformation” (Polanyi, 2001) – is required to reduce pressures on planetary boundaries while securing human wellbeing³. Competing pathways dominate current debates (Brand & Wissen, 2024): the ecological modernization or green growth project (Huber, 2000; OECD, 2011; World Bank, 2012) and the post-growth project (Eastwood & Heron, 2024; Jackson, 2011; Kallis et al., 2025; Nelson, 2025; Schmelzer et al., 2022). Second, social and environmental risks cannot be viewed in isolation. They are deeply interlinked and mutually reinforcing (Fritz & Lee, 2023, p. 316). The climate crisis – driven disproportionately by highly affluent groups (Chancel, 2022) – places the greatest burdens on the bottom half of the global income distribution, threatening to re-entrench inequalities to levels last observed in the 1980s (Bothe et al., 2025, p. 18). These dynamics underscore the necessity of an *eco-social nexus* (Domorenok et al., 2025a, p. 7) and demand expanding research on eco-social challenges and eco-social policy responses (Bohnenberger, 2023; Hirvilammi et al., 2023).

The demands of social-ecological transformation and the eco-social nexus form the foundation of the *research field* of *eco-social policy* and *sustainable welfare*. This field aims (a) to contribute to the vision of meeting basic needs within planetary boundaries (Büchs, 2021, p. 1; Fritz & Lee, 2023, p. 320; Gough, 2017, p. 86; Hirvilammi & Kortetmäki, 2025, p. 11; Koch

¹ In this master’s thesis, italics are used as a visual aid to make the content of paragraphs easier to recognize. This contrasts with other uses of italics, such as to indicate terms in a different document language.

² Within this thesis, the terms “ecological” and “environmental” are used interchangeably.

³ In line with Daly and Farley (2011, p. 6), the terms wellbeing and welfare are used interchangeably throughout this thesis.

& Mont, 2016b, p. 5) and (b) to develop policy instruments capable of addressing eco-social challenges and enabling sustainable welfare (Bohnenberger, 2023, p. 329; Fritz & Lee, 2023, p. 320; Gough, 2017, p. 161; Mandelli, 2022, p. 334).

In line with its societal relevance, the field has gained increasing *academic traction* (Bohnenberger, 2023, p. 329). Emerging at the intersection of social policy and sustainability research (Hirvilammi & Koch, 2020, p. 2) and closely linked to post-growth⁴ scholarship (Büchs, 2025, p. 169; Hirvilammi & Koch, 2020, p. 2; Koch & Mont, 2016b, pp. 203–204; Mandelli, 2022, p. 339), it has expanded considerably since early contributions identified the absence of coherent conceptual frameworks and research agendas (Koch & Mont, 2016b, p. 2). Collaborative platforms have been established (Mandelli et al., 2022), special issues were published in leading journals (Fritz & Lee, 2023; Hirvilammi & Koch, 2020), and new handbooks have consolidated theoretical, conceptual, and empirical advances (Domorenok et al., 2025c; Schulze Waltrup, 2025b).

Within this evolving landscape, scholarly attention has gradually shifted from justifying the eco-social nexus to *developing concepts* and concrete *policy designs* (Bohnenberger, 2023, p. 329). Recent work has advanced definitions and typologies of eco-social policies (Laruffa, 2024; Mandelli, 2022; Schulze Waltrup, 2025a) and has examined individual policy proposals such as universal basic income (UBI) (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023; Bohnenberger, 2020; Büchs, 2021; Langridge, 2024), universal basic services (UBS) (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023; Bohnenberger, 2020; Büchs, 2021), universal basic vouchers (Bohnenberger, 2020), WTR (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023; Persson et al., 2022), income and wealth caps (François et al., 2023), and eco-social labor market approaches (Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024; Neier et al., 2024). Yet, despite this shift, the field still lacks a systematic mapping of which eco-social policy proposals currently dominate academic discourse. Prior systematic reviews have focused on degrowth policy proposals (Cosme et al., 2017; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022), leaving the landscape of explicitly eco-social policy proposals insufficiently charted. As a result, claims about the prominence of specific policies in the field – such as those made by Fritz and Lee (2023, p. 321) – lack systematic empirical grounding.

Addressing this gap motivates the aim of this thesis⁵: to systematically map contemporary eco-social policies discussed in academic literature published between 2021 and 2025. The central

⁴ Within this thesis, I use the term post-growth to encompass the concepts of doughnut economics, wellbeing economics, steady-state economics, and degrowth, as described by Kallis et al. (2025, p. e62).

⁵ Within this thesis, I use the terms “(master) thesis” and “research (project)” synonymously.

research question is: *Which eco-social policy proposals are discussed in contemporary academic literature within the sustainable welfare and eco-social policy research field?* This question is examined through three sub-questions: (a) Which categories of eco-social policy proposals are most prominent? (b) Which individual proposals receive the most substantive attention? (c) Which ecological and social objectives are associated with these proposals and serve as the rationale for categorizing them as eco-social policy proposals?

These questions contribute to the *development* of the *research field* in multiple ways. Identifying prominent categories and proposals reveals underexplored areas and helps inform future research agendas. Examining the ecological and social objectives⁶ associated with each proposal allows for assessing the validity of existing eco-social policy concepts and supports their further refinement. The analysis also uncovers recurring eco-social argumentation patterns, enabling critical reflection on current conceptualizations.

To support this investigation, two *key concepts* require clarification: *sustainable welfare* and *eco-social policy*. Sustainable welfare refers to the satisfaction of basic needs within planetary boundaries. Planetary boundaries operationalize ecological limits by identifying key biophysical thresholds that define the “safe operating space for humanity” (Rockström et al., 2009). Basic needs theory provides the normative foundation on the social side, emphasizing universal and objective requirements for human wellbeing (Büchs & Koch, 2017, p. 62; Gough, 2017, pp. 45–46; Max-Neef et al., 1991, p. 19). Eco-social policies, drawing on contributions by Gough (2017), Mandelli (2022), Bohnenberger (2023), and Fritz and Lee (2023), are defined as public policies that simultaneously pursue environmental and social objectives. That is, they integrate the aims of environmental policy and social policy within a single policy. Within this thesis, eco-social policies encompass policies that follow at least implicit (outcome-oriented) ecological and social objectives (Mandelli, 2022, pp. 339–341). For example, basic income schemes primarily pursue social objectives but may indirectly reduce material consumption, thereby exhibiting implicit ecological effects (Khan et al., 2023, p. 1520).

These conceptual foundations provide the basis for employing a *systematic literature review* (SLR) as the methodological approach. The SLR approach is well suited to the aim of mapping an emerging and heterogeneous field, as it supports comprehensive and structured synthesis across large bodies of literature (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006, p. 2). Its transparent search and selection procedures enhance reliability and validity of findings (Wetterich & Plänitz, 2021, pp.

⁶ Within this thesis, I use “policy objective”, “policy end”, “policy goal”, “intended result” and “intended effect” interchangeably.

10–11). As such, the SLR approach is particularly appropriate for identifying the landscape of eco-social policy proposals and for critically assessing the development of the research field.

The remainder of the thesis proceeds as follows. Chapter 2 introduces the conceptual foundations: sustainable welfare and eco-social policies. Chapter 3 outlines and justifies the systematic literature review methodology. Chapter 4 presents the findings, covering both sample characteristics and the qualitative synthesis of eco-social policy proposals. Chapter 5 discusses these findings, focusing on the transformative potential of identified policies, conceptual issues in eco-social policy research, and the feasibility of implementation. Chapter 6 concludes by summarizing the key findings, outlining implications for future research, and reflecting on methodological limitations.

2. Theoretical Background

This chapter covers the theoretical foundations relevant to the research question, focusing on the two core concepts of sustainable welfare and eco-social policies. Together, these components establish the conceptual groundwork that informs the methodological approach presented in the subsequent chapter.

2.1. The Vision: Sustainable Welfare

The following definition draws on both seminal and recent contributions to the field, including Bohnenberger (2023) and Fritz and Lee (2023). In line with post-growth perspectives (Kallis et al., 2025, p. e62), I define sustainable welfare as...

the vision of universal human need satisfaction within planetary boundaries.

In the remainder of this chapter, the two core components of sustainable welfare are introduced: (a) *compatibility with planetary boundaries* and (b) the *satisfaction of basic needs*. To conceptualize planetary boundaries, I first briefly distinguish the concept from that of planetary wellbeing, then outline the planetary boundaries framework and its individual dimensions, and finally relate it to ecological critiques of economic growth. Regarding basic needs, I distinguish basic needs theory from subjective wellbeing theory, situate it within objective theories of wellbeing, and introduce two influential approaches: Max-Neef's (1991) needs theory and the needs theory developed by Doyal and Gough (1991).

2.1.1. Compatibility with Planetary Boundaries

Sustainable welfare fundamentally requires compatibility with planetary boundaries, a framework that operationalizes ecological limits thinking. Before examining planetary boundaries, it is necessary to distinguish this approach from the recently developed planetary wellbeing paradigm, which challenges anthropocentric framings.

Hirvilammi and Kortetmäki (2025) propose *planetary wellbeing* as a relational alternative grounded in three core principles (pp. 13–14): (a) material and energy flows constitute integral components of organismic metabolism; (b) human survival depends on earth's provisioning systems and processes; (c) humans needs satisfaction depends on relationships with human and non-human organisms. Despite advocating for this relational approach, the authors acknowledge that sustainable welfare research remains predominantly anchored in

anthropocentric normative frameworks, with planetary boundaries enjoying widespread analytical adoption (Büchs, 2021; Coote, 2022; Fritz & Lee, 2023; Gough, 2017; Koch, 2022).

The *planetary boundaries framework* explicitly adopts anthropocentric positioning, delineating critical biophysical thresholds that constitute a “safe operating space for humanity” (Rockström et al., 2009, p. 472). This safe operating space corresponds geologically to the Holocene, an epoch characterized by exceptional stability within central biophysical earth systems. Throughout this period, environmental variations remained within manageable parameters, enabling Earth's regulatory mechanisms to successfully adapt to changes. This regulatory success reflected the moderate nature of environmental fluctuations, whereby global average temperatures and biogeochemical cycles – including nitrogen and phosphorus inputs – experienced only minor oscillations (Rockström et al., 2009, p. 472).

Holocene stability faces unprecedented threats from human-driven environmental transformation, marking entry into the *Anthropocene* epoch wherein humans constitute the primary agents of planetary change (Crutzen, 2002). This transition coincides with the “Great Acceleration” (Steffen et al., 2015, p. 616) – the fossil-fuel industrialization period characterized by exponential increases in population, economic activity, and energy consumption (Zalasiewicz* et al., 2010). Current socio-economic trajectories are “reaching criticality” as they drive systematic environmental deterioration (Steffen et al., 2015, p. 620).

Responding to Anthropocene dangers, Rockström et al. (2009) developed the planetary boundaries framework to identify *critical Earth-system thresholds* defining humanity's safe operating space. This framework delineates subsystem stability limits, with thresholds indicating potential tipping points where systems transition abruptly between stable states. Such transitions often occur non-linearly and irreversibly, creating temporal urgency for boundary recognition and compliance to prevent catastrophic human welfare consequences (Rockström et al., 2009, p. 472).

The framework encompasses *nine planetary boundaries* essential for earth-system stability: climate change, ocean acidification, stratospheric ozone depletion, biogeochemical flows (nitrogen and phosphorus cycles), global freshwater use, land-system change, biosphere integrity, atmospheric aerosol loading, and novel entities (chemical pollution).

Biosphere integrity encompasses biodiversity preservation within Earth-system functioning, reflecting genetic diversity shaped through natural selection processes (Richardson et al., 2023, p. 3). *Climate change* measures global mean temperature increases, targeting containment

below 2°C above pre-industrial levels to avoid catastrophic tipping points including ice sheet collapse, sea-level rise, and agricultural system disruption, monitored through atmospheric carbon dioxide concentrations (Rockström et al., 2009, pp. 473–474).

Novel entities encompass synthetic substances including microplastics and radioactive materials such as nuclear waste. *Stratospheric ozone depletion* tracks atmospheric ozone layer degradation from industrial emissions, while *global freshwater use* quantifies human freshwater consumption (Richardson et al., 2023, pp. 6–7). *Atmospheric aerosol loading* measures particulate concentrations, and *ocean acidification* monitors marine pH changes. *Biogeochemical flows* address agricultural nutrient cycles, particularly nitrogen and phosphorus from fertilizer application, while *land-system change* tracks global land conversion patterns (Rockström et al., 2009, pp. 473–474).

Contemporary planetary boundary assessments reveal that six of nine critical thresholds have been transgressed, including land-system change and climate change, thereby destabilizing humanity’s safe operating space (Richardson et al., 2023). Land-system change manifests through accelerating *material throughput*, with the global material footprint quadrupling since 1970 (Lenzen et al., 2022). Domestic material consumption (DMC) – measuring total direct material use within economies – demonstrates alarming trajectories: between 2015 and 2022, per capita DMC increased approximately 15 percent while aggregate global DMC rose 23 percent, driven primarily by intensifying consumption patterns outpacing demographic growth (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2025, p. 33).

Regarding *greenhouse gas emissions* and climate boundary transgression, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change’s (2023) sixth assessment report identifies a critical emissions gap between current mitigation policies, national pledges, and pathways necessary to limit warming to 1.5°C or below 2°C, indicating humanity’s present trajectory remains incompatible with climate targets (p. 57). These planetary boundary transgressions necessitate systematic identification and transformation of critical human activities to restore compatibility with earth-system stability thresholds.

From an *ecological economics perspective*, planetary boundaries intersect fundamentally with economic growth, as economic activity remains intrinsically linked to environmental impact (Büchs, 2021, pp. 2–3). Following Schmelzer et al. (2022), the ecological critique of growth contends that “economic growth destroys the ecological foundations of human life and cannot be transformed to become sustainable” (p. 78), epitomized by the assertion that “infinite growth is not possible on a finite planet” (p. 79). This growth-critical position challenges the green

growth paradigm, which posits that economic expansion can continue through efficiency and consistency strategies⁷ enabled by technological advancement (Hickel & Kallis, 2020, p. 470; Schmelzer et al., 2022, p. 79). These contrasting paradigms reflect fundamentally divergent positions within the decoupling debate concerning whether economic growth can be separated from environmental degradation (Hickel & Hallegatte, 2022).

The *decoupling debate* can be analytically structured across three dimensions: (a) environmental degradation domains, distinguishing between greenhouse gas emissions and resource use; (b) technical feasibility, differentiating absolute decoupling (wherein environmental impact declines in absolute terms) from relative decoupling (wherein environmental impact grows more slowly than economic output); and (c) temporal feasibility, examining whether decoupling mechanisms can be implemented sufficiently rapidly to meet planetary tipping points and policy targets within necessary timeframes (Parrique et al., 2019, pp. 11–12).

Looking at *greenhouse gas emissions*, green growth requires absolute decoupling between economic growth and greenhouse gas emissions (Hickel & Kallis, 2020, p. 483). Empirical evidence shows that absolute decoupling of greenhouse gas emissions and GDP growth is technically possible. Historical accounts from 2005 to 2023 show that at least eighteen countries achieved absolute decoupling – applying both to production-based and consumption-based measurement methods (Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2023, p. 53). This evidence is pointing towards a green growth approach. However, Infante-Amate et al. (2025) points out that 40% of cumulative fossil-fuel CO₂ reduction from 1820 to 2022 can be accounted to five global crises and is thus somewhat questioning the feasibility of decoupling. Furthermore, post-growth proponents argue that temporal feasibility fails. Projections based upon highly optimistic decoupling rates indicate that decoupling is not sufficient to remain below the carbon budget, which holds global warming to 1.5°C to 2°C as set in the Paris Climate Agreement (Haberl et al., 2020, pp. 31–33; Hickel & Kallis, 2020, p. 483).

The debate is further polarized around the decoupling of economic growth from *resource use*.⁸ Green growth requires achieving absolute decoupling – a sustained reduction in resource use

⁷ The sustainability strategies of efficiency, consistency and sufficiency are further elaborated in the subsection “Environmental Policy”.

⁸ It is noted that resource use does not directly translate into environmental pressure but that well-established metrics of resource such as domestic material consumption enjoy robust empirical grounding (Krausmann et al., 2009, p. 2703).

alongside continued GDP growth (Hickel & Kallis, 2020, p. 483). However, empirical evidence challenges this assumption. Hickel and Kallis (2020, p. 475) recognize that while absolute decoupling may be technically feasible in the short term for high-income countries, it appears unsustainable over the long term. Supporting this, Ward et al. (2016, pp. 8–11) model that Australia could experience economic growth alongside declining material extraction until 2050, after which extraction levels are projected to rebound, eroding earlier efficiency gains. Acknowledging such limitations, some green growth advocates increasingly shift their focus away from the feasibility of decoupling and toward criticizing the post-growth project itself. For example, Warlenius (2023, p. 8) contends that implementing post-growth policies would necessitate a drastic economic contraction – approximately 90% in high-income countries and 70% in middle-income countries – rendering the scenario politically unfeasible.

Although the appropriate path forward remains contested – and this paper does not seek to adjudicate that debate – it is important to highlight two key areas of *common ground*. Both perspectives acknowledge the existence of the ecological crisis and advocate for solutions, distinguishing themselves from regressive-authoritarian positions that deny or downplay environmental problems. Both perspectives recognize that technological innovation is necessary and supportive of improving decoupling rates – differing primarily in their assessments of its feasibility and pace (Hickel & Kallis, 2020, p. 483).

2.1.2. Satisfaction of Basic Needs

Alongside planetary boundary compliance, basic needs satisfaction constitutes the second foundational component of sustainable welfare. Basic needs theory originates within *welfarism*, a philosophical framework grounded in consequentialist ethics that posits humans’ moral obligation to pursue optimal world states and the principle that “the world is made better just when the creatures in it are made better off” (Heathwood, 2014, p. 199). Welfare broadly denotes the “subjective condition of faring or doing well; in other words, what is ‘good for’ a person” (Brandstedt & Emmelin, 2016, p. 16). However, diverse wellbeing theories generate distinct policy implications (Gough, 2017, pp. 39–42). These theories bifurcate into subjective and objective approaches concerning wellbeing’s nature – a dimension requiring analytical distinction from theories addressing wellbeing’s sources (Brandstedt & Emmelin, 2016, p. 16; Büchs & Koch, 2017, p. 58).

Subjective wellbeing theories establish necessary connections between individuals and objects of value – encompassing desires, preferences, affections, or concerns (Heathwood, 2014, p. 202). Two prominent subjective frameworks merit examination: hedonism and desire theory.

Hedonism, sometimes conflated with eudaimonism (wellbeing as subjective happiness), fundamentally centers on mental experiences of pleasure (pursued) and pain (avoided). This theory privileges internal psychological states, identifying pleasure and pain as intrinsically valuable determinants of wellbeing while denying intrinsic significance to external circumstances – a position generating considerable philosophical controversy (Heathwood, 2014, pp. 207–208) (Heathwood, 2014, pp. 207–208).

Desire theory – alternatively termed preference satisfaction theory – posits that wellbeing “consists in getting what one wants” (Heathwood, 2014, p. 210). Contrasting with hedonism’s internalist orientation, preference satisfaction theory emphasizes external world engagement. Individuals may desire activities (playing chess) or social support (partner assistance), though internal experiences remain relevant insofar as preferences may target sensory experiences (tasting cuisine) or physical comfort (relieving throat irritation) (Heathwood, 2014, p. 210).

Preference satisfaction theory maintains particular prominence within neoclassical economics (Daly & Farley, 2011, p. 4). Welfare economics’ emergence saw economists adopting preference satisfaction frameworks as *utility theories*, primarily justified through measurement advantages: wellbeing becomes quantifiable through revealed preferences in market behavior, where prices coordinate individuals’ consumption desires (Daly & Farley, 2011, p. 3; Heathwood, 2014, p. 211). Free markets operating through supply-demand mechanisms ostensibly reveal individual preferences through observable, monetized choices (Brandstedt & Emmelin, 2016, pp. 18–19).

This preference revelation mechanism through market prices enables linking *economic activity* to *wellbeing*. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) measures economic activity by quantifying the monetary market value of all final goods and services produced within a country during specified periods (Daly & Farley, 2011, p. 228; Mankiw & Taylor, 2017, p. 9). Within this framework, higher per capita GDP enables greater preference satisfaction, ostensibly indicating enhanced wellbeing (Daly & Farley, 2011, p. 4). Consequently, “GDP-growth is practically the same as [...] progress, well-being” (Schmelzer, 2016, p. 13), signaling improved quality of life (van den Bergh, 2009, p. 117).

However, GDP's status as a wellbeing proxy peaked during the twentieth century, facing mounting *criticism* by the twenty-first century's onset. Critiques address inconsistent accounting practices, non-substitutability of basic needs (water, food, shelter), inadequate incorporation of happiness and income distribution, informal economy exclusion (van den Bergh, 2009, pp. 118–120), and even orthodox economists questioning GDP's validity as a wellbeing indicator (Schmelzer, 2016, p. 6).⁹ Those critiques are subsumed under the socio-economic critique of growth (Schmelzer, 2016, p. 94).

Contrasting with subjective theories of wellbeing, *objective theories* posit that certain life dimensions possess inherent value independent of individual attitudes or preferences. These intrinsically valuable elements remain good regardless of whether individuals desire or approve of them – they are attitude-independent (Heathwood, 2014, p. 202). Objective theories' principal advantage lies in their capacity to moralize welfare by incorporating ecological limits and extending evaluative scope beyond individual benefit to encompass “what is good for the community” (Brandstedt & Emmelin, 2016, p. 26) (Brandstedt & Emmelin, 2016, p. 26). Two prominent objective approaches merit examination: the *basic needs approaches* advanced by Manfred Max-Neef (1991) and by Len Doyal and Ian Gough (1984, 1991).

Max-Neef's (1991) theory adopts a systems perspective, conceptualizing needs as interrelated, non-hierarchically organized elements. His framework's foundational distinction separates needs from needs satisfiers (Max-Neef et al., 1991, p. 17). Needs themselves – termed axiological – encompass nine fundamental categories: subsistence, protection, affection, understanding, participation, identity, leisure, creation, and freedom. Each axiological need exists along a continuum between deprivation and actualization, representing need fulfillment states. Needs satisfiers, conversely, constitute the means through which axiological needs achieve satisfaction or remain deprived. Hunger exemplifies subsistence need deprivation, motivating individuals to employ a needs satisfier – food consumption – to achieve subsistence satisfaction. Similarly, appropriate housing satisfies protection needs while democratic participation fulfills participation needs. Although these examples suggest one-to-one correspondences, single satisfiers frequently contribute to multiple needs simultaneously (Koch & Buch-Hansen, 2016, p. 33).

⁹ Crucially, GDP was never conceptualized as a wellbeing proxy but rather as an economic activity measure, revealing nothing about activity's purpose or normative direction (Daly & Farley, 2011, p. 3; Ward et al., 2016, p. 12).

Needs satisfiers manifest across four existential categories: being, doing, having, and interacting. Physical health exemplifies the “being” category, food consumption the “doing” category, housing represents “having,” while democratic engagement constitutes “interacting.” This matrix of axiological needs and existential satisfier categories provides comprehensive analytical frameworks for evaluating human wellbeing (Max-Neef et al., 1991, p. 17).

Doyal and Gough’s (1991, p. 170) theory establishes hierarchical need structures centered on two basic needs (Figure 1: Hierarchical Basic Needs Theory): health and autonomy. These dual needs function as prerequisites for the overarching objective of minimally impaired social participation. Health encompasses both physical and mental dimensions enabling societal engagement. Autonomy, conceptualized as agency in decision-making and action, derives from individuals’ cognitive and emotional capacities, cultural knowledge (including linguistic competence), and access to socially meaningful activity options. Autonomy fundamentally concerns capacities for self-directed action and life responsibility (Koch & Buch-Hansen, 2016, p. 34).

Figure 1: Hierarchical Basic Needs Theory; adapted from Doyal and Gough (1991, p. 170)

Paralleling Max-Neef’s (1991) framework, Doyal and Gough (1991) identify universal satisfier characteristics – *intermediate needs* – enabling the satisfaction of health and autonomy. Those intermediate needs encompass nutritional food and clean water, protective housing, non-hazardous physical environments, non-hazardous work environment, appropriate healthcare, childhood security, significant social relationships, physical security, economic security, safe birth control and child-bearing, and adequate education (Doyal & Gough, 1991, pp. 157–158).

Intermediate needs provide *concrete guidance* for eco-social *policy design* (Hirvilammi & Kortetmäki, 2025, p. 17), with basic needs approaches demonstrating substantial capacity to inform public decision-making (Büchs & Koch, 2017, pp. 106–107; Gough, 2017, pp. 45–46). By establishing minimum satisfaction thresholds through expert codification and experiential knowledge (Gough, 2017, p. 50), needs theory enables distinguishing necessities from luxuries (Gough, 2017, p. 148), defining consumption corridors (Di Giulio & Fuchs, 2014), and specifying decent living standards (Rao & Min, 2018).

Needs theory's policy appeal derives from several *defining characteristics* scholars attribute to basic needs: first, needs are objective. For instance, drinking clean water and having protective housing are universal physiological requirements for human beings – while the concrete implementation varies from one culture to another at a given time (Büchs & Koch, 2017, p. 62; Gough, 2017, pp. 45–46; Koch & Buch-Hansen, 2016, p. 33; Max-Neef et al., 1991, p. 19). Second, needs are non-negotiable, since satisfaction failures fundamentally undermine human wellbeing (Brandstedt & Emmelin, 2016, p. 19; Gasper, 1996, p. 633; Gough, 2017, p. 46). Third, needs are finite (Gough, 2017, p. 46) – contrasting sharply with preference satisfaction theories premised on infinite desire expansion paralleling perpetual economic growth (Koch & Buch-Hansen, 2016, p. 33). While basic needs provisioning requires material goods and services, the concern centers on targeted economic activity meeting specific needs rather than maximizing aggregate production (Koch et al., 2017, p. 10). Fourth, needs are cross-generational (Gough, 2017, p. 46), providing a framework for addressing intergenerational conflicts inherent in social-ecological transformation (Büchs & Koch, 2017, pp. 106–107).

Needs theory has achieved significant *political* and academic *institutionalization*. Politically, the Brundtland Report (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987) embedded needs within sustainable development's canonical definition: “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (p. 43). Despite the report's conceptual vagueness regarding specific needs, this formulation established needs discourse within international development frameworks.

More substantively, needs theory has achieved *paradigmatic status* within sustainable welfare *scholarship* (Büchs & Koch, 2017, p. 64; Hirvilammi & Kortetmäki, 2025, p. 17). Needs-based wellbeing conceptions pervade sustainable welfare literature, constituting the field's dominant analytical framework (Bohnenberger, 2023; Büchs, 2021; Fritz & Lee, 2023). As Gough (2017, pp. 62–63) demonstrates, needs theories provide definitive criteria for minimally decent lives, serving as sustainable welfare's normative foundation for defining social objectives.

Having established basic needs as sustainable welfare's normative foundation, attention now turns to *operationalizing* this *vision*. Sustainable welfare pursues two interrelated objectives: (a) satisfying basic needs through appropriate satisfiers including protective housing, adequate nutrition, and meaningful social relationships; and (b) achieving planetary boundary compatibility through material throughput and greenhouse gas emissions reduction. These objectives constitute sustainable welfare's normative ends. The critical question concerns the means: how can the vision of sustainable welfare become reality? Sustainable welfare scholarship converges on a clear answer: *eco-social policies* (Bohnenberger, 2020, p. 5; Büchs, 2025, p. 169; Büchs & Koch, 2017, pp. 112–119; Gough, 2014, p. 127; Hirvilammi & Kortetmäki, 2025, p. 19).

2.2. The Instrument: Eco-Social Policies

The following definition draws on both seminal and recent contributions in the field, including Gough (2017), Mandelli (2022), Bohnenberger (2023), and Fritz and Lee (2023). In this thesis, eco-social policies are understood as...

public policies that simultaneously pursue environmental and social objectives – that is, they integrate the aims of environmental policy and social policy within a single policy.

This section elaborates the conceptual components necessary to define, understand, and distinguish eco-social policies. The definition above provides the organizing structure for the subsections that follow. I begin by outlining the policy nexus through an elaboration of (a) public policy, (b) environmental policy, and (c) social policy. I then introduce the eco-social nexus by examining (d) eco-social inequality and risk, and (e) eco-social policy.

2.2.1. Public Policy

Eco-social policies are *public policies*. Broadly, public policies refer to socially binding decisions within political systems (Wenzelburger & Zohlnhöfer, 2023, p. 2). They operate in the political-administrative system, which contrasts agents such as central banks, interest groups or organizations. The function of public policy is the processing of societal problems (by policy instruments) – pointing towards the substantive dimension of politics (Jann, 1985, p. 64).

Policies being the substantive dimension of politics can be distinguished from the procedural and structural dimensions of politics. The procedural dimension, which follows the term

politics, refers to the conflict-ridden negotiation process between different interests about objectives and goals (Jann, 1985, pp. 64–65). The structural dimension *polity* covers the institutions, meaning political ideologies, Rules and standards that characterize the framework for action of policy and politics (Schneider & Janning, 2006, p. 15). Hence, policies can also be described as the result of politics surrounded by polity.

With a narrow lens, public policies only refer to the results of policy formulation (Jann, 1985, p. 65). *Policy formulation* is one phase of the policy cycle. The policy cycle is an analytical lens onto public policies. It structures policy into the subsequent phases: problem definition, agenda-setting, policy formulation, policy implementation, policy evaluation (Jann & Wegrich, 2009, p. 86). The problem definition phase sets its focus on whether problems gain relevance and how they are defined in the political system. If a problem is defined and of relevance, it is set on the political agenda. The agenda setting phase has started. Here the importance of the problem shifts into focus, e.g. is it prioritized over other problems and is discussed in the agenda of the national parliament. The third phase is called policy formulation phase. Policy formulation covers the search for a solution to the problem – what policies are suitable for solving the problem. However, suitability of policies is not the only relevant indicator but also whether any likelihood of implementation exists. Majorities are a decisive factor for policy formulation. At the end of the policy formulation process stands the adoption of a law. However, even though a policy has been adopted, it has not been implemented. The fourth phase of the policy cycle covers policy implementation. Adopted policies still leave administrations room for maneuver in the implementation. This can affect the intended problem solving and lead to unintended side effects. Lastly, adopted and implemented policies are evaluated as regards their effects – making the fifth phase of policy evaluation (Wenzelburger & Zohlhöfer, 2023, pp. 4–7).

Even though policy evaluation is a phase in the policy cycle, the policy cycle also informs *policy evaluation*. The policy cycle can serve to differentiate interrelated policy effects: outputs, outcomes and impacts (Knill & Tosun, 2015, pp. 19–20). Policy outputs occur at the end of the formulation phase (3rd phase in the policy cycle) and are the result of political decision-making processes. As such, policy outputs are rather direct policy effects and linked to the specific content of a policy. For instance, an emission limit for industrial companies or a certain unemployment benefit level qualifies as policy output (Anderson, 2010, pp. 8–9). Policy outcomes become particularly discernible during the implementation phase, as this stage reveals whether the policy has produced the intended behavioral changes among the target group and administrative authorities. Put differently, outcomes denote the empirically

observable effects of policies within their specific regulatory domain. Returning to the example of an emission limit for industrial production, outcomes refer to whether and how the target group changed its behavior, e.g. complying with limit values by new filter technologies. Lastly, policy impacts build upon policy outcomes and cover effects that go beyond regulatory domain. The question of whether air quality improved by companies complying with the specified emission limits represents an evaluation of policy impacts (Knill & Tosun, 2015, pp. 19–20).

Having mentioned emission limits, they display another integral part of public policies: *policy instruments*. The policy instrument is the practical design of a policy. It refers to the governance principle used to pursue policy goals and change behavior (Wenzelburger & Zohlnhöfer, 2023, pp. 9–10). Windhoff-Héritier (1987, pp. 27–34) differentiate between five governance principles: (a) regulatory instruments, (b) (economic) incentives, (c) provisioning, (d) information-based instruments, and (e) exemplary function.

Regulatory instruments are instruments that aim to directly affect the behavior of individuals or organizations. Infringement of generally binding rules is threatened with sanctions. Infringing behavior leads to the risk of sanctions. Examples of such instruments can be found in criminal law or environmental policy (Wenzelburger & Zohlnhöfer, 2023, p. 10). In criminal law for instance, theft is prohibited and can be punished with imprisonment or fines. Regulatory instruments rely on the authoritative imposition of rules and sanctions, thereby exerting direct control over behavior. *Incentive-based instruments*, by contrast, operate through indirect mechanisms: they do not render particular actions illegal or subject to prosecution, but rather seek to align individual or collective behavior with policy objectives by altering the underlying structure of costs and benefits. In the realm of family policy, governments frequently implement child allowance programs – comprising regular monetary transfers to households per child – as a mechanism to influence fertility decisions and promote family formation. Similarly, environmental policy initiatives utilize financial instruments such as subsidies to incentivize private sector investment in environmentally sustainable technologies, thereby reducing the ecological impact of industrial production processes (Wenzelburger & Zohlnhöfer, 2023, p. 10). The third governance principle employs *state provisioning*, whereby government assumes responsibility for delivering essential services and infrastructure that citizens may utilize voluntarily. Unlike regulatory approaches, state provisioning exercises indirect behavioral influence through service availability. Public kindergarten provision exemplifies this mechanism, facilitating parental labor market participation by addressing childcare constraints (Wenzelburger & Zohlnhöfer, 2023, pp. 10–11). The fourth principle encompasses

information-based instruments that seek to modify individual or organizational behavior through persuasive communication and normative appeals. These interventions manifest in public awareness campaigns, including graphic health warnings on tobacco packaging and mandatory nutritional labeling on food products (Wenzelburger & Zohlnhöfer, 2023, p. 11). Finally, the most laissez-faire approach involves the *exemplary function* of government institutions, wherein policymakers demonstrate desired behaviors through personal conduct (Wenzelburger & Zohlnhöfer, 2023, p. 11). This mechanism operates when politicians promote cycling by commuting to parliament via bicycle (Zips, 2021) or advocate for high meat consumption by maintaining meat-based diets on social media platforms (Raether, 2025).

While governments possess theoretical power to steer public behavior through policy instruments, their *practical steering power* faces significant constraints, particularly in the context of economic globalization. Although policy instruments remain viable tools for achieving specific policy objectives, globalization has expanded exit options for corporations seeking to circumvent regulatory frameworks. This dynamic creates policy dilemmas wherein decision-makers may refrain from implementing stringent environmental regulations due to concerns about capital flight – specifically, the risk that firms will relocate production to jurisdictions with lower regulatory standards, potentially resulting in domestic employment losses (Wenzelburger & Zohlnhöfer, 2023, p. 11).

Having mentioned environmental regulation, public policies can be further categorized through the lens of distinct *policy areas* (Windhoff-Héritier, 1987, pp. 21–22). These domains encompass diverse governmental spheres including environmental policy, economic policy, social policy, and education policy. *Environmental policy* and *social policy* constitute the foundational components of the eco-social policy definition applied in this thesis and require further exploration in the subsequent subsections.

2.2.2. Environmental Policy

Environmental policy is concerned with the preservation and enhancement of natural living conditions (Meadowcroft, 2006, p. 111). It is characterized by both cross-sectoral and transboundary dimensions (Tosun, 2023, p. 710). Environmental policy is cross-sectoral since other policy domains such as economic policy, housing policy, and agricultural policy intersect with environmental concerns. This interrelation is increasingly recognized by political decision-makers, as evidenced by the Sustainable Development Goals (Tosun, 2023, pp. 724–725). It is transboundary, since environmental problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and

deforestation require international cooperation for effective solutions, thus necessitating international environmental policy (Meadowcroft, 2006, p. 7).

International environmental policy coincides with the development of national environmental policy (Tosun, 2023, pp. 710–711) and national environmental policy is linked to the emergence of the *environmental state*. The environmental state emerged in the mid-twentieth century alongside the political movement of environmentalism (Meadowcroft, 2006, p. 111). Since then, the state-led management of the environment, often regarded in terms of environmental protection and enacted through environmental policies (Brown & Chang, 2024, p. 4), has gained prominence and led to many different facets of environmental policy (Tosun, 2023, p. 711):

One facet regards the underlying *principles* of environmental policies. That is of relevance as the underlying principles guide the perception of environmental problems and the concrete design of environmental solutions. For instance, utilizing the precautionary principle allows policymakers to adopt rather restrictive measures to avoid the emergence of environmental issues (Tosun, 2023, pp. 711–712). And this points to another facet of environmental policy: instruments. Environmental policy uses a broad spectrum from (a) information-based instruments such as campaigns, over (b) regulatory instruments such as certificates to (c) economic incentives such as tax levies or subsidies. One paradigmatic regulatory instrument refers to environmental impact assessments, which require *ex-ante* evaluation of proposed infrastructure projects in terms of their environmental impact (Tosun, 2023, p. 712). The third dimension examines policy subject areas, differentiating between (a) discrete environmental domains such as land use, water resources, or air quality, and (b) multifaceted challenges such as sustainable development (Meadowcroft, 2006, p. 113).

It is outside the scope of this thesis to outline all subject areas and hence the focus is laid upon the one that has the greatest relevance in the field (Jörgens et al., 2023): climate change and climate policy. Prior to examining climate policies, it is essential to acknowledge that climate policy remains intrinsically linked to *energy policy*. In its narrow conceptualization, energy policy prioritizes energy supply security, recognizing energy as fundamental to modern societal functioning. Given that domestic energy resources within national territories are typically insufficient, nation-states experience substantial dependency on energy imports, creating vulnerabilities to geopolitical and economic fluctuations that may significantly compromise energy security. However, a broader conceptualization of energy policy encompasses its critical role in climate change mitigation through greenhouse gas emission reductions (Tosun, 2023,

pp. 713–714). Such climate mitigation can be pursued by three sustainability strategies: consistency, efficiency and sufficiency (Huber, 2000).

In the context of energy policy, *consistency* denotes the strategic commitment to transition away from fossil fuel dependency toward renewable energy sources, thereby enhancing the compatibility between the industrial and natural metabolism. Renewable energy technologies emit significantly fewer greenhouse gases than conventional fossil fuels such as coal, natural gas, and petroleum (Huber, 2000, p. 20). Accordingly, green energy policies prioritize the systematic expansion and integration of renewable energy infrastructure.

Efficiency, by contrast, pertains to policy objectives aimed at optimizing energy use to reduce overall electricity and thermal energy demand (Rudolf & Schmidt, 2025, p. 1). More broadly, efficiency strategies extend beyond the energy sector to include improvements in resource productivity, defined as “improving the input-output-relations of existing production processes and product chains” (Huber, 2000, p. 17).

While energy policies have traditionally emphasized efficiency and consistency, the principle of *sufficiency* has gained increasing attention as a necessary complement for effective climate change mitigation (Pichler et al., 2025, p. 8). As the third sustainability strategy, sufficiency entails the voluntary limitation of material and energy consumption (Huber, 2000, p. 11). From an ecological global perspective, sufficiency requires that global production and consumption – collectively determining material throughput – be reduced to levels consistent with planetary boundaries, thereby safeguarding the ecological conditions necessary for human survival and wellbeing (Iten et al., 2024, p. 1716).

The *sustainability strategies* of sufficiency, efficiency, and consistency extend beyond energy policy and are also applied within the broader context of climate change. From an anthropocentric perspective, climate change generates significant social risks that compel policy responses (Johansson et al., 2016, p. 103). Climate policies typically adopt a twofold strategy for addressing these risks: mitigation and adaptation (Gough, 2017, pp. 27–28). As the present thesis focuses on eco-social policy, it concentrates on mitigation policies, since adaptation currently plays a marginal role within sustainable welfare research (Bohnenberger, 2023, p. 336).

Climate mitigation policies seek to reduce carbon sources or enhance carbon sinks, ultimately contributing to the decarbonization of production and consumption in national economies worldwide (Gough, 2017, pp. 27–28). Within Coote’s (2012, p. 9) framework, such preventative

public interventions are conceptualized as upstream measures, addressing the root causes of carbon emissions rather than their downstream effects. Mitigation thus involves not only emission reduction but also the enhancement of natural and technological carbon sinks.

A prominent example of the latter is *carbon capture and storage* (CCS) – a set of technologies designed to remove greenhouse gases from the atmosphere. CCS is often presented as a key instrument for limiting global temperature rise to below 2 °C (Bui et al., 2018; Gizer et al., 2022; Leonzio & Shah, 2024). However, CCS remains highly contested (Määttä & de Gooyert, 2025, p. 1), particularly when contrasted with mitigation strategies that emphasize structural decarbonization of energy systems and societal institutions (Johansson et al., 2016, p. 103).

Such climate mitigation policies can be conceptualized by a recently developed supply- and demand-side *climate mitigation typology* by Pichler et al. (2025): The typology uses the entry point of intervention, which relates to demand-side or supply side, and the scope of intervention, which relates to systemic or individual, for conceptualizing four perspectives on how climate mitigation policies take shape: (a) techno-innovation, (b) individual decision-making, (c) industrial transformation, and (d) embedded lifestyles (Pichler et al., 2025, p. 3).

The *techno-innovation perspective* mainly follows a supply-side entry point and individual scope. Key policy instruments include tax cuts, subsidizing innovation and carbon pricing. As such they can be characterized as economic incentives (instruments) and take an economic or market approach to guiding the behavior of producing companies. Additionally, voluntary company commitments are also a key policy instrument from the techno-innovation perspective. The *individual decision-making perspective* is demand-sided and individual. Key policy instruments, that have the target mainly individuals, are information-based and incentive instruments. Both techno-innovation and individual decision-making perspectives show rather low-binding and incentive-based approaches. In contrast to that, the industrial transformation perspective and embedded lifestyles perspective opts for high(er)-binding, collective-rules-based measures.

The *industrial transformation perspective* is supply-sided and takes a systemic approach. Accordingly, the target actors are institutional such as states or municipalities but also corporations that are deeply inflected with fossil fuels, labor unions and climate movements. Key policy instruments cover command-and-control instruments, green industrial policy, green economic planning, public provisioning and sustainable welfare policies. Lastly, the *embedded lifestyles perspective* is demand-sided and systemic. Key policy instruments focus on spatial planning and mixing various command-and-control, information-based and incentive

instruments. The target group are individuals and households and partially institutional actors such as spatial planners (Pichler et al., 2025, pp. 3–5).

2.2.3. Social Policy

Social policy encompasses governmental interventions designed to enhance human wellbeing across fundamental domains including social security, education, healthcare, and housing provision (Huby, 1998, p. 2). Its primary objective involves delivering the resources and determinants necessary for societal welfare and individual wellbeing (Brandstedt & Emmelin, 2016, p. 16). Beyond this broad conceptualization, social policy fulfils the role of “managing social risks” (Esping-Andersen, 1995, p. 33).

Social risks encompass novel exogenous challenges facing social groups resulting from broader structural transformations within society (Hirvilammi et al., 2023, p. 3; Johansson et al., 2016, pp. 94–95). Crucially, these risks transcend individual circumstances, becoming collectivized concerns that require societal-level responses – demanding for social policies such as (a) regulatory instruments establishing protective frameworks through labor standards, minimum wage legislation, and employment security provisions; (b) state provisioning delivering essential public services including childcare infrastructure, healthcare systems, and employment support centers; and (c) redistributive measures, achieved through monetary transfers and progressive taxation systems that reallocate material resources across society (Häusermann, 2023, p. 590).

Nevertheless, substantial cross-national and temporal variation exists regarding which individual risks become collectivized as social risks and subsequently form social policies (Häusermann, 2023, pp. 591–592). Understanding these differences necessitates examining *welfare state typologies* and *temporal trajectories*, particularly within the Global North, thus contributing to understanding social policy – and social policy being fundamental to conceptualizing eco-social policies.

Following Esping-Andersen (1995, p. 1), welfare states can be systematically compared across two *analytical dimensions*: benefit generosity and distributive logic. Benefit generosity ranges from minimalist welfare states, which limit social policies to basic social insurance programs (Esping-Andersen, 1995, p. 141; Pierson, 2006, p. 10), to comprehensive welfare systems in the Global North that may even address transnational social risks extending beyond national boundaries (Gough, 2021, p. 902). Distributive logic distinguishes between egalitarian and stratifying approaches. The egalitarian approach prioritizes universalist principles where

redistributive measures play a central role in social provision. Conversely, the stratifying approach employs selective mechanisms regarding benefit entitlements, with such entitlements linked to proportional insurance contributions that reflect labor market participation and income levels (Häusermann, 2023, p. 591).

Examining the *temporal trajectory* of social policy development, welfare states emerged institutionally during the interwar period of the 1920s-1930s and subsequently expanded – despite temporary wartime disruption – until the retrenchment period of the 1970s-1980s (Béland et al., 2021, p. 7; Lessenich, 2008, p. 16; Nullmeier & Kaufmann, 2021, p. 94; Pierson, 2006, pp. 119, 146). This expansion encompassed simultaneous growth across three dimensions: social expenditure as a proportion of national budgets, population coverage within social security systems, and the range of recognized social risks requiring state intervention (Lessenich, 2008, p. 67). These developments collectively constitute what scholars term “the Golden Age” of welfare state development (Pierson, 2006, p. 129).¹⁰

This sustained *welfare state expansion* emerged from exceptionally high economic growth rates driven by the second industrialization (Koch, 2022, p. 449). Economic growth and welfare state development formed a mutually reinforcing relationship, with the welfare state evolving into a catalyst for further economic expansion (Lessenich, 2008, pp. 39–40). However, this symbiotic relationship must be contextualized within broader socio-economic transformations.

The welfare state’s emergence represented a *functional response* to industrialization-induced conflicts, inequalities, and risks that required systematic buffering and resolution through social policy interventions (Esping-Andersen, 1995, p. 19; Lessenich, 2008, p. 39). The risks addressed during this post-war period – termed “classic or first-generation social risks” (Johansson et al., 2016, p. 94) – encompassed old age, sickness, work-related accidents, unemployment, disability, and maternity (Häusermann, 2023, pp. 590–591; Johansson et al., 2016, pp. 94–95).

These contingencies threatened individuals’ capacity to maintain economic self-sufficiency for themselves and their dependents. The *social security* architecture reflected this concern by primarily orienting protection around the male industrial worker model, inadvertently placing

¹⁰ However, conventional Golden Age narratives often neglect critical analytical perspectives. On the one hand, welfare state development during this period remained predominantly nation-state centered, lacking meaningful international coordination or governance mechanisms (Nullmeier & Kaufmann, 2021, p. 105). On the other hand, conventional narrative reflects a distinctly Global North perspective that systematically overlooks Global South experiences and structural inequalities. The celebrated prosperity of the Global North was fundamentally enabled by – and continues to depend upon – the economic exploitation of the Global South (Nullmeier & Kaufmann, 2021, p. 5).

families at risk when traditional breadwinners faced these challenges (Häusermann, 2023, pp. 590–591). State provisioning became essential as industrialization eroded traditional welfare provision by extended families and communities while simultaneously expanding exposure to these social risks, making the welfare state a necessary functional adaptation to socio-economic modernization (Häusermann, 2023, pp. 595–596; Lessenich, 2008, p. 39).

While the economic growth-welfare state interdependence proved advantageous post-World War II, this relationship precipitated *welfare retrenchment* beginning in the 1970s. The oil crisis-induced recession created challenging macro-economic conditions for social policy (Lessenich, 2008, p. 16; Pierson, 2006, p. 146). Declining tax revenues combined with increased social security demand due to structural unemployment generated a fiscal crisis characterized by rising public indebtedness (Pierson, 2006, p. 153). By the 1980s, governments pursued neoliberal rather than Keynesian responses, implementing means-testing for universal benefits and shifting responsibility for social risk protection toward individuals through market-based welfare provision and family support systems (Béland et al., 2021, p. 7; Pierson, 2006, pp. 159–160).

Despite neoliberal persistence, ongoing *social change* continues *reshaping welfare states* through post-industrial economic transitions and intensified globalization (Hemerijck & Ronchi, 2021, p. 113; Johansson et al., 2016, p. 96). The emerging knowledge economy generates labor market risks particularly affecting medium and low-skilled workers while creating new employment forms including platform economy arrangements (Häusermann, 2023, p. 602). These developments have prompted dual policy adaptations:

First, achieving *full employment* – essential for fiscal sustainability – has become increasingly challenging, leading social policy toward capability enhancement and opportunity creation in post-industrial labor markets (Hemerijck & Ronchi, 2021, p. 113; Johansson et al., 2016, p. 96). This social investment approach prioritizes ex-ante employment enablement over ex-post income compensation (Häusermann, 2023, p. 602; Hemerijck & Ronchi, 2021, p. 12).

Second, *individualization* and *demographic shifts* have generated new social risks – a second generation distinct from industrialization-based predecessor risks (Bonoli, 2007, p. 520; Johansson et al., 2016, p. 94). Welfare states have incorporated these emerging risks through adjusted social security services and social investment paradigm adoption (Johansson et al., 2016, pp. 94–96).

Contemporary welfare states thus face multiple *intersecting crises* encompassing demographic transitions, migration pressures, and environmental degradation (Koch & Mont, 2016a, p. 2; C. C. Walker et al., 2021, p. 1). Consequently, twenty-first century social policy must refocus on addressing inequalities and conflicts emerging from environmental policies and climate change impacts (Hirvilammi et al., 2023, p. 2). This imperative necessitates examining the intersection of ecological and social challenges that characterize contemporary policy landscapes.

2.2.4. Eco-Social Inequality and Risk

The persistence of *environmental* and *social policies* within *separate* institutional silos generates substantial policy failures, given their profound mutual interdependencies (Bohnenberger, 2023, pp. 329–330; Koch & Fritz, 2014, p. 680). Isolated policy approaches can produce double injustice scenarios wherein the most vulnerable households disproportionately experience both climate crisis impacts and climate mitigation burdens, despite bearing minimal responsibility for environmental degradation (G. Walker, 2012, pp. 215–216). Conversely, welfare state mechanisms themselves generate environmental harm, since contemporary redistributive social policies enable individuals to maintain comparatively excessive ecological footprints (Koch & Fritz, 2014, p. 683; Meadowcroft, 2006, p. 33). These dynamics demonstrate the reciprocal interdependence characterizing environmental and social policy domains.

This interdependence manifests most prominently in the relationship between *climate change* and *inequality*, particularly regarding the distribution of responsibility for emissions and the burden of climate consequences (Mandelli et al., 2022, pp. 340–341).

Regarding *responsibility*, inequality research reveals profound carbon inequalities that fundamentally structure environmental responsibility. Hubacek et al. (2017, p. 3) demonstrate severe disparities between carbon emissions and income distribution, calculating that in 2010 the global top 10% of the income table generated 36% of global carbon emissions while the bottom 50% contributed merely 15%. Such severe disparities are confirmed and even have worsened following Chancel (2022). He finds that in 2019 the global top 10% generated 48% of carbon emissions while the bottom 50% contributed merely 12%. Within developed economies, per-capita emissions from low- and middle-income groups have declined since 1990, contrasting sharply with increased emissions among the global top 1%. This pattern reflects broader wealth-concentration dynamics, as Apeti et al. (2025) establish that wealth concentration significantly exacerbates carbon inequality. Furthermore, Hubacek et al (2017, p.

4) reveal that income growth of the middle class in the developed world, necessary for decent living standards, would add another 0.6 °C to global warming by the end of the century. Consequently, multiple scholars advocate for far-reaching (lifestyle) changes grounded in sufficiency principles, particularly of global elites, as essential for reconciling basic needs satisfaction within planetary boundaries (Hubacek et al., 2017, p. 5; Millward-Hopkins et al., 2020, p. 9; Millward-Hopkins & Oswald, 2023, p. e153; Wiedmann et al., 2020, p. 7).

Regarding the *distribution* of climate change effects, effects can be differentiated between direct effects and indirect effects of climate change on inequality and social risks:

Extensive research demonstrates climate change's *direct effect* on *inequality*, particularly economic inequality. Burke et al. (2015) establish the fundamental linkage between economic activity and global climate, projecting that current warming trajectories will intensify global income inequality. Diffenbaugh and Burke (2019) reveal that climate change has already exacerbated between-country economic inequality through a parabolic temperature-growth relationship: cooler countries (predominantly Global North) benefit from rising temperatures while warmer countries (predominantly Global South) experience economic losses – effectively transferring climate costs from high-emission to low-emission regions. Similarly, Palagi et al. (2022) demonstrate that climate-induced extreme precipitation events intensify within-country income inequality, particularly in high-agricultural-intensity economies.

Extreme levels of precipitation only represent one instance of extreme weather events. Climate change amplifies the likelihood of extreme weather events and temperatures (Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change, 2023), with these events eventually manifesting as *social risks* including food insecurity (Jägermeyr et al., 2021; Leisner, 2020) and poverty growth (Hallegatte & Rozenberg, 2017; Mani et al., 2018). However, risk distribution remains profoundly unequal, as economically vulnerable populations bear disproportionate climate burdens (Hallegatte & Rozenberg, 2017, p. 250). Climate catastrophes compound existing poverty through wealth destruction, creating poverty traps wherein “shocks can keep people in poverty by making it more difficult for households to accumulate assets, regularly wiping out their stock of assets” (Hallegatte & Rozenberg, 2017, p. 250). This pattern manifests across developed economies: socially vulnerable UK communities face heightened flood exposure (Rözer & Surminski, 2021; Sayers et al., 2018), while German low-income households experience – relative to their available income – disproportionate flood damage compared to affluent households (Osberghaus, 2021).

Beyond direct climate impacts, *indirect effects* emerge from *climate policies* themselves, creating unintended social consequences. A comprehensive SLR demonstrates that most climate policies fail to generate positive social outcomes (Lamb et al., 2020), with mitigation measures typically creating winners and losers wherein the “working poor” are likely to be on the losing end (Johansson et al., 2016, pp. 106–106).

This pattern reflects the *regressive* nature of many *climate policies*, particularly incentive-based instruments. Carbon taxation exhibits regressive tendencies across multiple contexts (Linden et al., 2024; Vona, 2023), with home energy carbon taxes demonstrating regressive effects throughout Europe (Barker & Köhler, 1998; Sommer & Kratena, 2020). Low-income households face disproportionate burdens as energy costs constitute larger income proportions, potentially precipitating energy poverty characterized by inadequate access to essential energy services (González-Pijuan et al., 2023).

Revenue recycling mechanisms offer potential solutions, with financial compensation capable of reducing inequality (Johansson et al., 2016, p. 104). However, financial compensation may undermine emission reduction objectives by increasing consumption capacity. An alternative approach to financial compensation such as equal per capita cash rebates for home energy are universal green vouchers for renewable electricity and public transport (Büchs et al., 2021).

Climate policies generate additional indirect effects through *job displacement* during energy system transformation. While renewable energy sectors create long-term employment opportunities, transition periods precipitate substantial job losses in carbon-intensive industries, generating regional disparities where coal extraction and petrochemical regions face disproportionate impacts due to fundamental business model obsolescence (Johansson et al., 2016, p. 104). Europe’s net-zero transition leads to projected 300,000 job eliminations across coal and oil sectors through 2050, despite overall energy employment expansion from 1.3 million to 2.5–3 million positions. However, spatial, temporal, and skills misalignments between declining and emerging sectors create just transition challenges for displaced workers (Emmerling et al., 2025).

Climate change is a novel, system-wide social risk – *an eco-social risk* – that fundamentally alters risk distribution across societal groups (Gough, 2013, p. 185; Hirvilammi et al., 2023, pp. 3–4). Johansson et al. (2016, pp. 105–107) advance a parallel argument, contending that eco-social challenges necessitate an expanded risk conceptualization extending beyond both traditional first-generation social risks and second-generation risks associated with postindustrial transformation. Climate change’s threats to human wellbeing differ qualitatively

from the industrial and postindustrial social risks that have historically structured welfare state responses (Johansson et al., 2016, p. 102). By directly and indirectly transforming the nature of social risks themselves, climate change destabilizes established risk categories. Consequently, Johansson et al. (2016) argue that “the separation between social risks and climate risks in policy discourse needs to be overcome” (p. 106), signaling the emergence of eco-social policy as a distinct policy domain integrating environmental and social welfare objectives.

2.2.5. Eco-Social Policy

The *eco-social policy domain* emerges from recognition that environmental and social policies operating within separate institutional silos prove inadequate for addressing interconnected eco-social challenges. These challenges necessitate coherent rather than parallel policy approaches that integrate environmental and social objectives (Brown & Chang, 2024, p. 2; Büchs & Koch, 2017, p. 119; Domorenok et al., 2025b, p. 168; Gough, 2014, p. 127; Hirvilammi & Koch, 2020, p. 2). Johansson et al. (2016, p. 105) extend this logic further, advocating for an “eco-social lens” across multiple policy domains to anticipate and prevent eco-social side effects through coordinated policy design – potentially mitigating social risks while enhancing societal acceptance of environmental measures. Eco-social integration has consequently become a defining characteristic of eco-social policy scholarship (Hirvilammi & Kortetmäki, 2025, p. 12; Mandelli, 2022), providing the conceptual foundation for how eco-social policies are defined within this thesis.

Policy integration broadly refers to policy measures that simultaneously pursue objectives from traditionally separate domains (Rayner & Howlett, 2009, p. 100; Trein et al., 2019, p. 333), thereby challenging the hierarchical prioritization of specific policy goals (Mandelli, 2022, p. 340). Such integration operates by combining policy instruments that function symbiotically to achieve multiple ends (Rayner & Howlett, 2009, p. 100). However, the feasibility of designing synergistic instruments depends fundamentally on goal compatibility. Mandelli (2022, p. 337) distinguishes three compatibility scenarios: synergistic goals, trade-off goals, and incompatible goals. Synergistic integration occurs when policy objectives mutually reinforce one another – for example, combining environmental energy efficiency targets with social adequate housing goals through energy-efficient social housing retrofits. Trade-off integration arises when conflicting goals necessitate compensatory mechanisms, such as green reskilling programs that balance decarbonization imperatives against employment security for coal industry workers. Finally, certain policy goals are fundamentally incompatible and cannot be reconciled through trade-offs. For instance, the pursuit of continued global income growth conflicts with

aggregated reductions in greenhouse gas emissions necessary for restricting global warming (Infante-Amate et al., 2025).

Despite these integration challenges, environmental and social policies share *structural characteristics* that facilitate their convergence (Gough et al., 2008, p. 3): both policy domains address long-term societal challenges – escalating climate crises and widening inequalities respectively; both confront resource scarcity – climate policy manages limited carbon budgets while social policy allocates finite welfare resources, typically conceptualized as economic capital; both have achieved political institutionalization through the welfare state and environmental state apparatuses; both operate within growth-dependent political economies that constrain policy options. These parallels create favorable conditions for integrating environmental and social policy objectives.

Beyond compatibility frameworks, eco-social policies can be distinguished by their *integration direction* – whether they originate from primarily environmental policies with social elements or, primarily social policies with environmental elements (Krause, 2021, p. 332; Mandelli, 2022, pp. 341–343). These directional approaches reflect policy genealogies and normative orientations that shape eco-social policy design.

Socially-extended environmental policies – referring to primarily environmental policies with social elements – originate within environmental policy frameworks and incorporate social welfare dimensions to ensure equitable distribution of environmental transition costs and benefits (Krause, 2021, p. 332). This approach connects closely to just transition frameworks (Domorenok et al., 2025b, p. 167; Mandelli, 2022, pp. 338–339), though *just transition* itself remains conceptually contested. The Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change (2022) defines just transition narrowly in environmental scope but broadly in social terms: “a set of principles, processes and practices that aim to ensure that no people, workers, places, sectors, countries or regions are left behind in the transition from a high-carbon to a low-carbon economy” (p. 1806). Conversely, alternative framings adopt expansive environmental perspectives while focusing social concerns specifically on labor dimensions – what Bell (2020) characterizes as “working class environmentalism.” For present purposes, just transition broadly encompasses the “debate about how to have decent work without overstepping planetary limits” (Bell, 2020, p. 154).

Three *justice concepts* emerging from environmental policy scholarship inform socially-extended environmental policy design (Mandelli, 2022, pp. 338–339). Climate justice addresses the distribution of climate change impacts and mitigation burdens across social groups,

households, and individuals. Energy justice extends human rights frameworks across energy systems' full lifecycles, from resource extraction through consumption. Environmental justice, the most encompassing concept, emphasizes participatory governance in environmental lawmaking and policy implementation (Heffron & McCauley, 2018, p. 74).

Socially-extended environmental policies can further be conceptualized through “*socializing*” the *environmental state* – integrating social welfare considerations into environmental governance (Mandelli, 2022, p. 341). Three policy types emerge: (a) reactive policies addressing ecological catastrophe impacts (e.g., heatwave or wildfire relief); (b) ex post compensation for negative social effects of previously implemented climate policies; and (c) proactive policies distributing transition costs and benefits through deliberate design.

Environmentally extended social policies – referring to primarily social policies with environmental elements – originate within social policy frameworks and incorporate environmental sustainability objectives, connecting fundamentally to sustainable welfare paradigms (Mandelli, 2022, p. 339). While sustainable welfare encompasses broader theoretical terrain,¹¹ this directional approach specifically addresses critiques of welfare states' environmental impacts and pursues strategies for incorporating ecological limits into welfare provision (Hirvilammi, 2020, pp. 7–9).

“*Greening*” the *welfare state* adopts preventative orientations toward ecological degradation, aiming to reduce environmental footprints of both welfare state operations and citizens' consumption patterns enabled by welfare provisions (Hirvilammi, 2020, pp. 7–9; Mandelli, 2022, p. 341). Gough's (2017, p. 201) influential framework outlines gradual transitions from green growth approaches toward post-growth welfare systems capable of reconciling human wellbeing with planetary boundaries.

Having established eco-social integration and integration direction as foundational conceptual dimensions, a third critical aspect of eco-social policy conceptualization requires examination: the distinction between *implicit* and *explicit* definitional approaches. Mandelli (2022) provides the primary analytical framework for this distinction (Figure 2: Contrasting Definitional Approaches to Eco-Social Policy).

¹¹ See section “Sustainable Welfare”.

Figure 2: Contrasting Definitional Approaches to Eco-Social Policy; own figure

Implicit eco-social policy definitions adopt outcome-based and normative orientations, emphasizing policies’ “ability to achieve certain outcomes” (Mandelli, 2022, p. 339) and their “expected social and environmental impacts” (Mandelli, 2022, p. 340) rather than formally stated objectives. Khan et al. (2023, p. 1520) illustrate this approach through policies classified as eco-social based on anticipated outcomes: wealth and income caps theoretically enhance social cohesion while reducing environmentally damaging luxury consumption; basic income and working time reduction (WTR) ostensibly facilitate care work expansion while decreasing material production and consumption. Mandelli (2022, p. 340) characterizes this line of thought an outcome-based approach to eco-social policy identification.¹²

Conversely, *explicit* eco-social policy definitions require direct formulation of both ecological and social objectives within policy design, constituting what Mandelli (2022, p. 340) terms an output-based and non-normative approach. This definitional strategy offers distinct methodological advantages for empirical policy analysis: first, explicit objective formulation enables systematic identification of eco-social policies within policy landscapes – particularly valuable for policy document analysis as demonstrated by Mandelli (2022) and Cotta (2025). Second, explicit definitions facilitate evaluation of adopted and implemented policies, providing clear criteria for ex post assessment studies Mandelli (2022, p. 340).

Despite these analytical strengths, this thesis adopts *implicit definitional criteria* for identifying eco-social policies. This approach allows for a more comprehensive mapping of the eco-social

¹² See subsection “Public Policy” for different policy effects, including outputs, outcomes and impact.

policy landscape in current academic discourse. It aligns directly with the research aims by enabling the systematic identification of policies based on their social and environmental objectives, thereby maintaining analytical rigor.

The rationale is that implicit criteria permit a *broader* and more *inclusive identification* of eco-social policies.¹³ In contrast, relying solely on explicit definitional criteria would impose strict qualification thresholds, likely excluding many relevant publications and policy proposals. Such exclusions would narrow the analytical scope and undermine the goal of capturing the diversity and breadth of the contemporary eco-social policy field.

Multiple considerations support this rationale: first, eco-social policy scholarship constitutes an emerging research field (Bohnenberger, 2023, p. 329), where policy proposals remain under theoretical development, making explicit objective formulation less prevalent. Second, as Mandelli (2022, p. 340) acknowledges, most scholars within the field employ implicit definitional frameworks, including research on prominent policy proposals such as WTR, UBI, UBS, and wealth and income caps (Bohnenberger, 2020; Brandl & Zielinska, 2020; Büchs, 2021; Khan et al., 2023). Third, this thesis analyzes peer-reviewed academic articles rather than official policy documents.¹⁴ Academic publications typically present policy proposals conceptually without comprehensive design specifications, making identification of explicitly formulated environmental and social objectives improbable – a fundamental contrast with policy document analysis methodologies.

Summary

This chapter has set out the theoretical foundations relevant to the research question by elaborating the two core concepts of sustainable welfare and eco-social policies. In this thesis, sustainable welfare is defined as the vision of universal human need satisfaction within planetary boundaries. The planetary boundaries framework, grounded in an anthropocentric perspective, specifies nine biophysical thresholds – among them climate change, land-system change, and biosphere integrity – that delineate a safe operating space for humanity. Basic needs are situated within objective theories of well-being. Drawing on Doyal and Gough's theory, the overarching aim is minimally impaired social participation, which depends on the fulfillment of the two basic needs of health and autonomy. These, in turn, require the satisfaction of intermediate needs such as adequate housing, nutritious food, and economic security. Both

¹³ Using implicit and outcome-based definitional criteria encompasses the identification of explicit and output-based policies, since outcomes depend on outputs.

¹⁴ See section "Eligibility Criteria".

compliance with planetary boundaries and the satisfaction of basic needs are closely connected to critiques of economic growth, reflecting, respectively, ecological and socio-economic lines of critique.

Alongside sustainable welfare, eco-social policies constitute the second key conceptual pillar of this thesis. Eco-social policies are defined as public policies that simultaneously pursue environmental and social objectives. Conceptually, they draw on three policy domains: public policy, understood as socially binding decisions within political systems implemented through instruments such as regulation, economic incentives, and public provision; environmental policy, which aims to preserve and enhance natural living conditions and, in the case of climate policy, employs strategies of consistency, efficiency, and sufficiency; and social policy, which seeks to enhance human well-being through the management of social risks. However, treating environmental and social policy as separate domains is increasingly inadequate in light of emerging forms of eco-social inequality and eco-social risk. This necessitates integrated eco-social policies capable of addressing these interlinked challenges. Such policies typically take the form of either environmentally-extended social policies or socially-extended environmental policies. To capture this diversity, the thesis adopts implicit definitional criteria for identifying eco-social policies, as this broader approach enables a more comprehensive and analytically useful mapping of the eco-social policy landscape in contemporary academic discourse.

3. Methodology: Systematic Literature Review

Having established the conceptual foundations of sustainable welfare and delineated the contours of eco-social policies, the question arises as to which methodological approach is most suitable for addressing the central research question: *Which eco-social policy proposals are discussed in contemporary academic literature within the sustainable welfare and eco-social policy research field?*

To address this question, this thesis employs a SLR that follows the guidelines by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement (Havránek et al., 2020; Page et al., 2021). The following sections encompass the methodological appropriateness, eligibility criteria, search strategy and qualitative content analysis of the SLR.

3.1. Methodological Appropriateness

Systematic literature reviews provide structured approaches for capturing, categorizing, and analytically synthesizing extensive literature within defined research domains (Wetterich & Plänitz, 2021, p. 14). The following characteristics position SLR as an appropriate and effective methodological choice for this research project:

The principal strength of SLR lies in generating *comprehensive, structured overviews* of defined literature bodies, enabling researchers “[to make] sense of large bodies of information” (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006, p. 2). This synthesizing capacity serves a dual purpose: identifying knowledge gaps and mapping future research directions while simultaneously exposing areas of “false certainty” – solidified arguments resting on limited empirical foundations (Page et al., 2021, p. 2; Petticrew & Roberts, 2006, p. 2).

It needs to be emphasized that SLR’s capacity for managing information abundance assumes *heightened importance* given exponential scholarly production increases over recent decades. Research shows that scientific growth rate accounts to slightly above four percent with a doubling time of 17 years (Bornmann et al., 2021). This trend is likely to be accelerated by the use of artificial intelligence and large language models in scientific research (Madanchian & Taherdoost, 2025).

SLR’s strength of information management proves particularly *suitable* for this *research context*, given this thesis’s objective to map contemporary academic discourse on prominent policies. A preliminary Web of Science (WoS) search using field-related terms yields 390

publications and shows demonstrates notable publication growth.¹⁵ This indicates that the research aim requires engaging with substantive publication volumes – a requirement that SLR methodology fulfills.

Beyond managing information volume, SLRs provide transparent, replicable research processes through systematic documentation of search strategies, eligibility criteria, and analytical procedures (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006, pp. 5–6; Wetterich & Plänitz, 2021, p. 17). This *methodological transparency* enhances findings’ reliability and validity. (Page et al., 2021, p. 2; Wetterich & Plänitz, 2021, pp. 10–11). This is relevant, since scientific research tends to produce contradictory findings across studies addressing common questions (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006, pp. 5–6). One example is the dispute between green growth and post-growth proponents (Hickel & Hallegatte, 2022).¹⁶ Those contradictory findings tend to emerge in unsystematic literature reviews, which are typically conducted by field experts possessing substantial domain knowledge (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006, pp. 5–6). However, researcher expertise alone proves insufficient for generating unbiased, reliable syntheses (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006, pp. 5–6). Applied to the research aim of thesis – identifying dominant eco-social policies within scholarly discourse and illuminating how the discourse defines and justifies policies as “eco-social” – an unsystematic approach seems inappropriate. Instead, SLR methodological transparency proves particularly salient for eco-social policy research, where policies’ very characterization as “eco-social” remains contested and partially vague (Mandelli 2022; Laruffa, 2024).¹⁷

SLRs constitute a *well-established methodological approach* in sustainable welfare and eco-social policy research. Several influential studies have adopted comparable designs, including Lamb et al. (2020), N. Fitzpatrick et al (2022) and Bohnenberger (2023). While all three provided useful methodological reference points, Bohnenberger’s (2023) contribution is particularly valuable because it offers extensive documentation of the review process and clearly formulated, replicable protocols. The present thesis therefore draws on a set of accepted, field-validated methodological standards and adapts them to the specific requirements of the research question.

SLR methodology requires *specific preconditions* despite its appropriateness for this research context. Most critically, SLR demands clearly defined research questions. SLR proves

¹⁵ WoS query: ((TS = “eco-social policy”) OR (TS = “sustainable welfare”)).

¹⁶ See subsection “Planetary Boundaries”.

¹⁷ See subsection “Eco-Social Policy”.

unsuitable for projects aiming merely to summarize topics broadly; unsystematic approaches including narrative reviews better serve such purposes. Conversely, focused research questions enable systematic evidence examination across substantial publication corpuses. Petticrew and Roberts (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006, p. 10) draw instructive parallels between surveys and SLRs: surveys systematically examine populations while SLRs systematically examine literature. This thesis centers on precisely formulated research questions meeting SLR requirements. The central research question is: Which eco-social policy proposals are discussed in contemporary academic literature within the sustainable welfare and eco-social policy research field? This question is examined through three sub-questions: (a) Which categories of eco-social policy proposals are most prominent? (b) Which individual proposals receive the most substantive attention? (c) Which ecological and social objectives are associated with these proposals and serve as the rationale for categorizing them as eco-social policy proposals?

In summary, SLR methodology's capacity for synthesizing extensive literature combined with its procedural transparency establishes it as an appropriate and productive methodological approach for this research context. This justification enables proceeding to specific eligibility criteria.

3.2. Eligibility Criteria

Eligibility criteria constitute a core SLR component, determining whether publications warrant further analysis or fall outside the research question's scope. These criteria – encompassing both inclusion and exclusion parameters – should be maximally explicit and comprehensive to enhance findings' reliability. Ideally, secondary reviewers independently test eligibility criteria, enabling primary authors to refine specifications (Wetterich & Plänitz, 2021, p. 32).¹⁸

This study applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria shown in Figure 3 “Eligibility Criteria”.

¹⁸ While methodologically valuable, this master's thesis context precludes collaborative reviewer involvement given single-authorship requirements.

Figure 3: Eligibility Criteria; own figure

Journal publications constitute the included *type of study*. All included publications must be peer-reviewed. Conversely, books, book chapters, and reports (gray literature) were excluded from analysis.

The decision to focus on academic journal literature while omitting reports rests on three rationales: first, the research question targets critical analysis of the academic research field rather than politically circulating policy proposals, making scholarly literature the appropriate corpus. Second, (peer-reviewed) academic publications typically maintain higher methodological rigor and data quality than organizational reports. Third, academic journal literature presents a more manageable corpus compared to the vast proliferation of reports from diverse political organizations, including advocacy and lobbying groups.

Peer-reviewed journal publications offer two primary advantages: quality assurance through editorial review processes and representation of contemporary field scholarship. While books and book chapters might appear suitable, they tend to exhibit longer publication lag times between knowledge generation and dissemination compared to journal articles (Ewart, 2023, pp. 159–161), potentially excluding recent developments central to mapping current discourse.

Eligibility criteria should derive from research questions (Wetterich & Plänitz, 2021, p. 33). Accordingly, the *focus of study* centers on eco-social policies, which constitute the research question’s primary subject. Following precedents established by Bohnenberger (2023) and

Lamb et al. (2020), healthcare and nutrition policy studies were excluded given these subfields' already substantial research depth, which falls outside this thesis's scope.

Theoretical frameworks established in the subsection "Eco-Social Policy" require operationalization into practical inclusion requirements across two dimensions: policy scope and policy objectives. *Policy scope* addresses whether publications substantively explore or analyze public policies. Publications focusing exclusively on private sector initiatives (NGO programs, corporate policies) rather than public policy were excluded, as were studies examining politics or polity rather than policies. Included publications must address public policies, understood as binding governmental decisions within political systems, manifested through regulatory instruments, economic incentives, direct provisioning, information-based instruments, or exemplary state functions.¹⁹ Public policies at any governance level – international, national, regional, or local – qualify for inclusion, ensuring comprehensive coverage across policy scales.

Policy objective criteria determine whether publications contain eco-social policies – defined theoretically as policies integrating both social and ecological objectives. Publication inclusion requires evidence of dual dimensions: social and ecological. These dimensions are operationalized through specific indicators derived from the theoretical frameworks.

Social indicators encompass welfare (state/provisioning), wellbeing, basic needs, employment, poverty, justice, social security, and social risks. Ecological indicators include environmental (state), climate (change/mitigation), greenhouse gas emissions, decarbonization, biodiversity, sustainability (consistency/efficiency/sufficiency), resource and energy use, and planetary boundaries. Given potential implicitness in policy objective articulation, initial screening applies these criteria generously and inclusively. Stricter evaluation occurs during full-text analysis, where explicit integration of both dimensions receives verification. Nevertheless, it needs to be pointed out that peer-reviewed publications rarely state policy objectives with the clarity typical of policy documents. To reach a sufficient number of publications to be analyzed and eco-social policy proposals to be found, indicators such as policy expectations and observed policy effects were also used to infer policy objectives. Publications explicitly claiming to address eco-social policies received automatic consideration for full-text screening.

As regard to the *geographical scope*, only publications addressing eco-social policies within the context of the Global North were included. This means that policies implemented in or

¹⁹ See subsection "Public Policy".

designed for geographical entities belonging to the Global South were excluded.²⁰ The rationale for this restriction is threefold: first, welfare and environmental state architectures differ substantially between the Global North and Global South (Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024, pp. 249–250), which limits comparability. Second, the research field of eco-social policy and sustainable welfare is currently predominantly shaped by European scholarship (Mandelli et al., 2022, p. 305), making a Northern focus analytically coherent.²¹ Third, this restriction reflects the resource limitations inherent in a single-author master’s thesis.

3.3. Search Strategy

The search strategy followed a two-pronged approach, drawing on: (a) the EcoWelfare Zotero database (EW), and (b) the WoS.

The *EW database*, titled “Sustainable Welfare and Eco-Social Policies Network”, is curated by the “EcoWelfare Network” (Eco-Welfare: Sustainable Welfare and Eco-Social Policy Network, 2025b). The EcoWelfare Network was established in 2018 and was a merger of two existing scholarly communities – namely, the “Sustainable Welfare Network” and the „ESPAnet Eco-Social Policy Group” (Mandelli et al., 2022, p. 305). The database includes diverse publication types – books, book chapters, gray literature, and particularly journal articles. Initially compiled for the Network’s first newsletter (December 2022), the database has been continuously updated, with the most recent edition published in May 2025. As of May 2025, it contains approximately $n = 655$ entries, most of which were published between 2022 and 2025. Although the database is not an official bibliographic index, it indicates holding high disciplinary relevance: the database is maintained by a network that is led by some of the most prominent scholars in the field, including Katharina Bohnenberger, Benedetta Cotta, Tuuli Hirvilammi, Matteo Mandelli, Robin Schulze Waltrup, and Katharina Zimmermann (Eco-Welfare: Sustainable Welfare and Eco-Social Policy Network, 2025a). Their expertise indicates that the database accurately reflects core debates and current developments in eco-social policy research.

²⁰ It is noted that the terms “Global North” and “Global South” are geo-historical concepts and not strictly geographical (Bull & Banik, 2025, p. 195). Global North refers to high-income-level, industrialized, mostly northern hemisphere countries while the Global South to low-income-level, less industrialized predominantly in southern hemisphere countries (Kowalski, 2021, p. 389).

²¹ From a postcolonial perspective, this also points to the need for a more diverse research field that better represents scholars from the Global South, while critically interrogating the predominance of Global North research priorities.

Complementing this, the *WoS* served as another primary source for peer-reviewed academic literature. A Boolean search strategy was applied and refined through several iterative test rounds to optimize recall and precision (Wetterich & Plänitz, 2021, pp. 43, 51). An overview of all test rounds can be found in Appendix B “Search String Overview”. The final search string was: “eco-social polic*” OR “sustainable welfare” OR (“environmental polic*” AND “social polic*”) OR “sufficiency polic*”.²²

The *temporal scope* was limited to January 1, 2021 – April 29, 2025, extending Bohnenberger’s (2023) systematic review, which covered literature up to 2021. This update enables the identification of emerging trends and gaps in eco-social policy scholarship, particularly eco-social policy proposals, since that period.

The *selection process* was conducted in two consecutive phases (Wetterich & Plänitz, 2021, pp. 59–61). The first phase involved systematic screening of titles and abstracts to assess whether each publication met the inclusion criteria. Based on this initial assessment, publications were categorized according to their level of relevance. Publications were classified as *highly relevant* when an eco-social policy or policies represented a central focus explicitly reflected in both the title and abstract. Publications were considered of *medium relevance* when eco-social policy was the main focus in the abstract, while *low relevance* was assigned to studies that only indirectly or briefly addressed the topic. Those with no relevance lacked any substantial reference to eco-social policy and were therefore excluded. In cases where the degree of relevance remained ambiguous after abstract screening, a full-text review was conducted to ensure accurate classification. This stepwise categorization facilitated a structured overview of the research landscape and enabled efficient prioritization of studies in line with the resource constraints of this project.

The second phase consisted of *full-text screening and coding*. Publications that did not satisfy the inclusion criteria – particularly those failing to engage with eco-social policy – were excluded from further analysis. The remaining publications formed the empirical basis for the qualitative content analysis, which served as the synthesis method (Wetterich & Plänitz, 2021, p. 67). No automation tools were employed at any stage of the process. As this study constitutes an independent master’s thesis, all stages of screening and coding were carried out by a single researcher.

²² Query link to chosen WsoS search is [here](#).

3.4. Qualitative Content Analysis

Given the research question's focus on identifying eco-social policies proposed in contemporary peer-reviewed literature, quantitative or mixed-methods approaches prove unsuitable. Instead, *qualitative content analysis* serves this analytical purpose. This methodological choice aligns with approaches employed by established field research including articles by Lamb et al. (2020), N. Fitzpatrick et al. (2022), and Bohnenberger (2023), indicating methodological validation.

The *coding procedures* followed Rädiker and Kuckartz's (2019, pp. 102–105) methodological framework, adopting inductive rather than deductive approaches to category development. Inductive approaches generate categories directly from source material, constructing hierarchical classification systems through iterative analytical processes (Rädiker & Kuckartz, 2019, p. 98).²³

As regards to *analysis procedures*, two steps were undertaken: individual and cross-publication analysis. *Individual publications* constituted the initial analytical units. First, all publications classified as core publications underwent systematic scanning for potential eco-social policy proposals. Identification criteria required policies to (a) constitute public policies and (b) reference both ecological and social dimensions – with both having been established in “Eligibility Criteria” subsection.

Importantly, analysis drew not only upon primary literature (final sample publications) but also, when necessary, upon literature cited within sampled publications. This approach enabled the qualitative depth necessary for identifying eco-social policy proposals while addressing persistent ambiguity regarding “‘what counts as data' or 'findings'?” (Thomas & Harden, 2008, p. 4).

Subsequently, analytical units shifted from individual publications to *cross-publication synthesis*. All potential eco-social policy proposals were synthesized across publications, distinguishing and consolidating policy proposal names, definitions, variations, ecological objectives, and social objectives. Based on these synthesized proposals, overarching policy proposal categories were inductively generated and ranked by research intensity in descending

²³ It is noted that partial qualitative content analysis was already conducted during eligibility assessment of all publications. See section “Eligibility Criteria”.

order (Appendix C “MAXQDA Coding Snippet”). Given resource constraints, only the five highest research intensity categories qualified for detailed reporting in the chapter “Findings”.

Summary

This chapter has outlined the methodological approach adopted to address the central research question: a SLR conducted in accordance with PRISMA guidelines. An SLR represents a strong methodological fit, as it enables the production of comprehensive and structured overviews of clearly defined bodies of literature, ensures a high degree of methodological transparency, and reduces the risk of selection bias.

Methodological transparency was ensured through explicitly defined eligibility criteria. Included publications were peer-reviewed journal articles that focus on eco-social policies understood as public policy interventions pursuing both social and environmental objectives, and that are proposed within the context of the Global North. The search strategy followed a two-pronged approach, drawing on the EW database and the WoS.

Publications retrieved from EW and WoS subsequently underwent a two-stage selection process: first, titles and abstracts were systematically screened for relevance. Second, publications were categorized according to their level of relevance, distinguishing between highly relevant, medium relevant, and low-relevance contributions.

Finally, the qualitative content analysis followed an inductive logic. Analytical categories were derived directly from the source material and organized into a hierarchical classification system through an iterative coding process. The inductive analysis proceeded in two steps, consisting of within-publication analysis followed by cross-publication synthesis.

4. Findings

This chapter presents the results generated through the SLR. It is structured in two parts: first, the characteristics of the final sample are outlined, providing an overview of the publications included in the analysis. Second, the qualitative synthesis of eco-social policy proposals is presented, detailing the policy categories, policy proposals, and associated ecological and social objectives identified in the reviewed literature.

4.1. Sample Characteristics

Building on the methodological approach and eligibility criteria outlined above, the search and selection process yielded the following results (Figure 4: PRISMA Graph).²⁴

Figure 4: PRISMA Graph; adapted from Gräbner-Radkowitz & Strunk (2023, p. 3)

The following part presents the search and selection results for the WoS database, followed by those for the EW. Subsequently, the process of merging both databases and the outcomes of the full-text screening are reported.

The search and selection procedure using the *WoS database* identified a total of 169 publications. Following the title and abstract screening, 109 publications were excluded for not meeting the inclusion criteria. This screening left 60 publications deemed relevant. Among

²⁴ The list of all samples is available upon request from the author.

these, 15 publications of high relevance, 26 of medium relevance and 19 of low relevance (Appendix D: “All Databases”: Excel sheet “WoS”).

The *EW database* search produced a more extensive set of results. The full database contained 655 entries (Appendix D: “All Databases”: Excel sheet “EW unclean”), which were subsequently consolidated into a working sample of 332 publications for title and abstract screening (Appendix D: “All Databases”: Excel sheet “EW clean”). The consolidation involved several exclusion steps: 93 publications were removed because they did not meet the study-type criterion (i.e., only peer-reviewed journal articles were retained, while reports or books were excluded). For example, the OECD report “Who Pays for Higher Carbon Prices? Illustration for Lithuania and a Research Agenda” (Immervoll et al., 2023) and the book “Eco-Welfare and the Energy Transition: Themes and Debates for an Emerging Interplay” (De Vidovich, 2024) were excluded on this basis. Additionally, 205 duplicate records were removed, alongside four entries with incomplete bibliographic information and eight publications written in languages other than English or German. Thirteen further entries were excluded for not being peer-reviewed, such as articles from the Green European Journal, IDOS Policy Brief, and Stato e mercato.

Following the title and abstract screening of the working sample, 244 publications were excluded for not meeting the inclusion criteria – for example, Aleksandrova et al. (2024), which focused on climate finance in the Global South rather than the Global North. Furthermore, the screening process resulted in 86 relevant publications, categorized by relevance as follows: 24 highly relevant (e.g., Theodoropoulou et al. (2024) “National Eco-Social Policies in the Framework of EU Just Transition”), 30 moderately relevant (e.g. Gerstenberg (2024) “Ideas in Transition? Policymakers’ Ideas of the Social Dimension of the Green Transition”), and 32 of low relevance (e.g., Standal et al. (2023) “Can renewable energy communities enable a just energy transition? Exploring alignment between stakeholder motivations and needs and EU policy in Latvia, Norway, Portugal and Spain”).

Subsequently, the preliminary samples from both databases were merged, resulting in a combined dataset of 146 publications that included both matching and non-matching duplicates (Appendix D: “All Databases”: Excel sheet “Merged sample consolidation”). Matching duplicates – such as François et al. (2023) were removed. Non-matching duplicates, where publications had been categorized differently across databases, were reassessed based on the coding guideline. For instance, Laruffa (2022) was categorized as low relevance in the EW sample but medium relevance in the WoS sample; after full-text screening, it was ultimately

classified as low relevance. The removal of duplicates and re-evaluation of categorizations resulted in the exclusion of 45 publications, yielding a merged sample of 101 publications with 24 highly relevant, 32 moderately relevant, and 45 of low relevance (Appendix D: “All Databases”: Excel sheet “Pre-preliminary sample”).

Due to time constraints, the low-relevance publications were excluded, leaving 56 publications for detailed full-text screening of eco-social policies (Appendix D: “All Databases”: Excel sheet “Preliminary sample”). During this process, one publication – Kaufmann et al. (2023) – was removed, as it did not explicitly address a social dimension but only environmental dimension of respective policies. Ultimately, resource limitations led to a further narrowing of the dataset, resulting in a final sample of 23 publications (Appendix D: “All Databases”: Excel sheet “Final sample”). These were fully coded according to the research objectives.

Before turning to the results of the qualitative content analysis, the *main characteristics* of the final and pre-preliminary sample are summarized and depicted in the following figures.²⁵

The first study characteristic is the *publication year* (Figure 5: Publication Year).

Created with Datawrapper

Figure 5: Publication Year; own figure

²⁵ In the following paragraphs, I draw on publications from the final sample and also from the pre-preliminary sample. Percentages are reported as whole numbers.

Within the pre-preliminary sample, publications peaked in 2023 ($n = 36$; 36%), followed by 2024 ($n = 30$) and 2022 ($n = 22$), which together represent more than half of all publications. The years 2021 and 2025 show comparatively low publication numbers. A similar pattern appears in the final sample: publications again peaked in 2023 ($n = 8$; 35%), with 2022 and 2024 accounting together for 52% ($n = 7$ and $n = 5$, respectively). Only three publications were from 2021 and 2025 combined.

The second study characteristic explored is the *publication outlet* (Figure 6: Publication Outlet).

Created with Datawrapper

Figure 6: Publication Outlet; own figure

In the pre-preliminary sample, environmental policy-related journals were the most represented ($n = 32$; 32%),²⁶ led by “Energy Research & Social Science” ($n = 18$) and “Climate Policy” ($n = 5$). Social policy journals accounted for 28% ($n = 28$),²⁷ with “Social Policy and Society” ($n = 8$) and “European Journal of Social Security” ($n = 6$) most frequent. Sustainability-related

²⁶ Climate Policy, Energies, Energy Research & Social Science, Environment Development and Sustainability, Environmental Research Letters, Environmental Science & Policy, Environmental Sociology, Journal of Cleaner Production, Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning.

²⁷ Critical Social Policy, European Journal of Social Security, Global Social Policy, International Journal of Comparative Labour Law and Industrial Relations, Journal of European Public Policy, Journal of European Social Policy, Journal of Social Policy, Politiche Sociali, Social Policy and Society, Transfer: European Review of Labour and Research.

outlets comprised 22% (n = 22),²⁸ dominated by “Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy” and “Ecological Economics” (each n = 9). Broadly social science outlets made up 19% (n = 19)²⁹. In the final sample, sustainability-related journals represented the largest share (n = 8; 35%), followed by social policy (n = 7; 30%), environmental policy (n = 4; 17%), and social science (n = 4; 17%) outlets.

The third study characteristic reported on is the *publication database* (Figure 7: Publication Database).

Created with Datawrapper

Figure 7: Publication Database; own figure

Regarding the publication database, 45% of the pre-preliminary sample derived from the EW database, 33% appeared in both databases, and 23% were unique to the WoS. In the final sample, more than half (52%) were identified in both databases, while 35% were exclusive to the EW database and 12% to the WoS. This shift suggests that combining databases enhanced the overall robustness and quality of the dataset, as publications jointly identified by both sources were more likely to align with the research objectives and standards of the field.

²⁸ Ecological Economics, Gaia-Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society, Sustainability, Sustainability Science, Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy.

²⁹ Buildings & Cities, Contemporary Social Science, Culture, Practice & Europeanization, European Political Science, Futures, Historical Social Research Vol. 47, Journal of Common Market Studies, Journal of Critical Realism, Politische Vierteljahresschrift, Regional Studies, Regulation & Governance, Zeitschrift für Politikwissenschaft.

4.2. Qualitative Synthesis of Eco-Social Policy Proposals

Moving to the results of the qualitative synthesis, the analysis is structured around the central research question: *Which eco-social policy proposals are discussed in contemporary academic literature within the sustainable welfare and eco-social policy research field?* This question is further unpacked through three sub-questions: (a) Which categories of eco-social policy proposals are most prominent? (b) Which individual proposals receive the most substantive attention? (c) Which ecological and social objectives are associated with these proposals and serve as the rationale for categorizing them as eco-social policy proposals?

The findings of *eco-social policy proposals* are structured in the following way. First, identified policy proposals are systematically categorized using inductively derived typologies: basic income policies, working time policies, basic service policies, wealth and income regulation policies, and labor market policies. Each category is briefly outlined and linked to specific policy proposals identified within the literature.

For each policy category, at least one proposal demonstrating substantial analytical depth receives detailed examination, explicating both its ecological objectives and social objectives. This dual-objective analysis provides the analytical foundation for characterizing policies as eco-social policies. Additionally, policy proposals are classified according to *research intensity* – determined by citation frequency and qualitative analytical depth – into three tiers: core proposals (high research intensity), semi-core proposals (medium research intensity), and periphery proposals (low research intensity). This classification enables identification of well-established versus emerging eco-social policy approaches within the scholarly discourse.

The analysis focuses on eco-social policy proposals within the five policy categories demonstrating highest research intensity. Within these categories, detailed examination of both ecological and social dimensions is reserved for proposals possessing sufficient analytical depth within the literature. This selective approach reflects the scope constraints inherent to master's thesis research. Complete documentation of all identified eco-social policy proposals and additional categories remains available in the MAXQDA project file, accessible upon request to the author. Figure 8 “The House of Eco-Social Policy Proposals” provides an overview of all identified eco-social policy proposals alongside their research intensity.

Figure 8: The House of Eco-Social Policy Proposals; own figure

4.2.1. Basic Income Policies

The policy proposal category with very high research intensity can be summarized under the term *basic income policies*. Such eco-social policies refer to conditional and unconditional cash transfers (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 14). The analyzed literature covers four eco-social policies within this category: UBI, PI, transition income, and eco-social voucher. Eco-social vouchers denote targeted, non-cash transfers that can be used for environmentally or socially sustainable goods and services (Bohnenberger, 2020, p. 2). Transition income refers to temporary income support enabling individuals to engage in socially or ecologically valuable activities during sustainability transitions (Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024, p. 302; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022a, p. 515). However, eco-social vouchers and transition income are discussed only marginally, making them peripheral policy proposals. In contrast, UBI and PI are examined in greater depth and are therefore elaborated in detail.

Universal Basic Income (UBI)

UBI constitutes a *core policy proposal* within the eco-social literature. It is analyzed across eleven analyzed publications and thus demonstrating high research intensity (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023; Büchs, 2021; Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024; Dukelow, 2022; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022a; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022; François et al., 2023; Laksevics et al., 2025; Langridge, 2024; McGann & Murphy, 2023; Neier et al., 2024). UBI “refers to the payment of an unconditional income to everyone in society,” functioning as a state-administered cash provision that grants recipients consumptive autonomy over market-accessible goods and services (Büchs, 2021, pp. 1–2).

The *social dimension* of UBI is primarily associated with direct welfare objectives. At its core, the UBI seeks to guarantee all individuals a secure income that enables access to essential goods and services required for the satisfaction of basic needs. Ensuring the fulfilment of these needs represents a central normative goal of the UBI (Büchs, 2021, p. 4; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 7). Another key objective concerns the enhancement of individual autonomy through the decoupling of income security from wage labor (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 9; Büchs, 2021, p. 4; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 21³⁰). By weakening the dependence on paid employment, UBI is expected to enable recipients to reduce their working hours and to reallocate their time toward “social and political participation” (Langridge, 2024, p. 5), “socially useful work” (Dukelow, 2022, p. 502), “social reproduction” (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 9), “sustainable participation” (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 510), “convivial work” (Dukelow, 2022, p. 501) and “meaningful activities” (Büchs, 2021, p. 4). In this sense, UBI is associated with both a reduction in working time and an expansion of activities oriented toward the common good. Beyond these linkages, several authors also connect UBI more broadly – albeit without specifying causal mechanisms – to the reduction of social inequality (François et al., 2023, p. 1; Langridge, 2024, p. 1³¹) and the facilitation of a post-growth economy (N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 8; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 510).

The *ecological rationale* for the UBI is often articulated only implicitly and remains secondary to its social objectives. However, linked to ecological critiques of growth within post-growth discourse, UBI is recurrently framed as a potential mechanism for reducing material and energy throughput, thereby supporting a transition toward more sustainable patterns of production and consumption (Büchs, 2021, p. 1³²; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 510; Langridge, 2024, p. 3; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 21).

The reasoning on consumption mirrors the reasoning of the social objectives of the UBI. Greater time autonomy among recipients enables a shift toward activities and consumption patterns that meet genuine needs (Büchs, 2021, p. 5). These genuine needs are generally less materially intensive than previous forms of “unnecessary material consumption” (Langridge, 2024, p. 3). The labor supply argument suggests that the UBI may lead to a reduction in aggregate employment through more part-time work arrangements, which in turn could decrease overall consumption and consequently lower material and energy use (Büchs, 2021, p. 8; McGann &

³⁰ (Parijs, 1995)

³¹ (Weeks, 2011)

³² (Coote & Percy, 2020; T. Fitzpatrick & Cahill, 2002)

Murphy, 2023, p. 21³³). Other train of thoughts highlight potential effects related to reduced inequality (Büchs, 2021, p. 5; Langridge, 2024, p. 4³⁴) and increased green employment as an indirect outcome of UBI (Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024, p. 9³⁵).

Participation Income (PI)

A second major basic income proposal is the *PI*. The *PI* is at least mentioned or even discussed in six of the 23 analyzed documents (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023; Büchs, 2021; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022; Langridge, 2024; Laruffa et al., 2022; McGann & Murphy, 2023) and shows medium research intensity. Hence it can be classified as a “*semi-core policy proposal*”.

In contrast to UBI, *PI* is a conditional income grounded in principles of reciprocity (Büchs, 2021, p. 4; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 23). The cash transfer depends on participation in socially, ecologically, or democratically valuable activities (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 510) or other forms of “socially useful work” (McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 22). The scope of eligible activities varies and may include “education, care, voluntary work, political participation, life-long learning, reproduction, satisfying essential needs unmet by the market and environmental reproduction” (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 511). This conceptual flexibility allows for more specific variants such as an eco-social *PI*, which emphasizes reproductive and ecological forms of labor (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 511³⁶; Laruffa et al., 2022, p. 516; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 17³⁷), or a care income, which remunerates caregivers, thereby recognizing the economic and social value of care work and potentially alleviating the ongoing “crisis of care” (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 9³⁸; Langridge, 2024, p. 6³⁹).

The *social dimension* of *PI* is primarily linked to direct and explicit social objectives. Similar to the UBI, *PI* seeks to guarantee a basic needs-sufficient income while enhancing individual autonomy through the decoupling of income security from wage labour (Laruffa et al., 2022, pp. 510–512). Furthermore, the requirement to engage in socially valuable activities constitutes a social objective in itself (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 510).

³³ (McKay, 2011)

³⁴ (Gough, 2017; Veblen, 2005; Wilkinson & Pickett, 2011)

³⁵ (Bohnenberger, 2022)

³⁶ (Swaton, 2018)

³⁷ (Pérez-Muñoz, 2018; Swaton, 2018)

³⁸ (Global Women’s Strike, 2020)

³⁹ (Kallis et al., 2020)

In contrast to the UBI, the *environmental rationale* of PI is more explicitly articulated, as ecological forms of participation are expected to contribute to reducing environmental degradation (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 511; Laruffa et al., 2022, p. 510). However, unlike the UBI, PI is not associated with mechanisms such as reduced material consumption or lower aggregate employment leading indirectly to diminished environmental pressures.

4.2.2. Working Time Policies

The eco-social policy category with the second-greatest analytical depth can be summarized under the term *working time policies*, also referred to as “time politics” (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 8). Originating in social policy, working time policies encompass both working time redistribution and WTR (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 512). Within the reviewed literature, eco-social policy proposals addressing working time distribution include eco-social job sharing (Neier et al., 2024, p. 10), parental and paternity leave (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 513) and part-time family allowance (Neier et al., 2024, p. 10).

Working time distribution policies are discussed only marginally, positioning them as peripheral policy proposals. In contrast, the majority of discussions on working time policies focus on WTR (Dukelow, 2022, p. 501; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 8; Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 12; Neier et al., 2024, p. 10), which is consequently identified as a core policy proposal and analyzed in greater detail.

Working Time Reduction (WTR)

Hanbury et al. (2023, p. 2) distinguish WTR policies according to their *extent* (total number of working hours), *form* (daily, weekly, or annual reductions), and the degree of *wage compensation*. However, the studies reviewed do not consistently address all these dimensions, and the overall specificity of policy formulations remains limited.

Several publications refer to the right to part-time work. Two studies mention this right only in passing (N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 8; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 515), whereas Persson et al. (2022, p. 85) examine a right to part-time policy implemented in Sweden in greater depth. This policy is characterized as voluntary and flexible, accompanied by a proportional income reduction.

Other studies explore the form dimension of WTR by examining shorter working weeks – particularly the four-day week (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 512; Jenny et al., 2024, p. 5; Persson et al., 2022, p. 91) – or the implementation of shorter working days (Dukelow &

Murphy, 2022, p. 512). Variations in the extent of working hours are also discussed, including proposals for a 35-hour week (Persson et al., 2022, p. 83; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 512) and a 21-hour week (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 512⁴⁰). Interestingly, Dukelow and Murphy (2022, p. 513) also identify early retirement as an alternative form of WTR.

WTR is conceptually linked to both social and ecological objectives, producing what Persson et al. (2022) refer to as a potential “double dividend” (p. 81):

On the *social dimension*, WTR aims to enhance individual wellbeing through greater temporal autonomy and improved health outcomes (Hanbury et al., 2023, p. 8). The underlying theory of change suggests that reducing working hours increases leisure time and time prosperity (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 512; Jenny et al., 2024, p. 10; Persson et al., 2022, p. 84), which in turn allows for (a) more time spent with family, friends, and physical activity – factors associated with greater wellbeing (Persson et al., 2022, p. 89⁴¹) – and (b) more time devoted to unpaid care work, ideally distributed more equally between men and women (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 12). Overall, WTR is portrayed as a mechanism for improving work–life balance (Laksevic et al., 2025, p. 6; Persson et al., 2022, p. 84⁴²).

Beyond temporal autonomy, WTR is also associated with multiple health benefits. The literature highlights improvements in mental health and reductions in burnout risk (Persson et al., 2022, p. 81–84⁴³; Hanbury et al., 2023, p. 4–5⁴⁴). Moreover, WTR is found to alleviate work–family conflicts, contributing to broader psychosocial wellbeing (Hanbury et al., 2023, p. 5).

In addition to its social objectives, WTR is associated with several ecological goals. Broadly, the underlying argument is that shorter working hours can contribute to lower ecological footprints (Persson et al., 2022, p. 84). The literature identifies two primary mechanisms explaining this relationship: the income effect and the time effect.

The income effect suggests that reduced working hours typically entail lower disposable income, leading to decreased consumption and, consequently, lower environmental impacts (Persson et al., 2022, p. 84; Hanbury et al., 2023, p. 8; Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 12⁴⁵). The time effect, by contrast, posits that individuals with more free time engage in less

⁴⁰ (Coote et al., 2010)

⁴¹ (Killingsworth & Gilbert, 2010)

⁴² (Gunderson, 2019; Parrique, 2019)

⁴³ (Coote et al., 2020; Kasser & Sheldon, 2009)

⁴⁴ (Neubert et al., 2022)

⁴⁵ (Schor, 2005)

environmentally intensive activities (Persson et al., 2022, p. 84; Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 6). For example, greater temporal flexibility may encourage slower modes of mobility – such as cycling instead of car commuting – thereby reducing emissions (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 13⁴⁶).

Beyond these two mechanisms, several studies argue that WTR may indirectly lower productivity levels, which can reduce aggregate environmental pressures associated with production (Hanbury et al., 2023, p. 7; Jenny et al., 2024, p. 5). Finally, building on both consumption- and production-side dynamics, three studies connect WTR to broader post-growth transformations, suggesting that shorter working hours facilitate a societal shift toward economic models operating within planetary boundaries (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 12; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 512; Dukelow, 2022, p. 503).

4.2.3. Basic Service Policies

The eco-social policy category with the third greatest analytical depth can be summarized under the term *basic service policies*, which predominantly encompass UBS. UBS represents a core eco-social policy proposal and is further elaborated on.

Universal Basic Services (UBS)

UBS can be defined as “the identification of basic needs, the collective organization of goods and services required to satisfy those needs, and the provision of free access to them” (Büchs, 2021, p. 2). Following Coote (2022, p. 474), UBS can also be conceptualized as a broader framework comprising the following three elements: needs-orientation, collective provisioning, decommodification.

First, UBS are characterized by an explicit focus on needs, a feature emphasized across multiple studies (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 10; Büchs, 2021, p. 1; Coote, 2022, p. 474; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022b, p. 511; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022; Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 8; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 20). Second, the question of how services are provided is addressed through collective provisioning. In this model, the state acts as a facilitator of high-quality need satisfaction (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 511⁴⁷) while responsibility for provision is shared between public and non-state actors (Coote, 2022, p. 475). Third, UBS involve the decommodified or free provision of essential goods and services, including healthcare,

⁴⁶ (Knight et al., 2013)

⁴⁷ (Coote & Percy, 2020)

childcare, housing, energy, education, public transport, water, food, and internet access (Büchs, 2021, p. 3; Coote, 2022, p. 475; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022b, p. 515; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 7; Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 9). Nevertheless, the literature reveals variation in which services should be universally accessible, and which may remain within market exchange (Coote, 2022, p. 475; Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 8). Given this conceptual diversity – particularly regarding the scope and mode of service provision – the subsequent analysis of social and ecological objectives refers broadly to UBS as an umbrella policy proposal.

The *social dimension* of UBS is articulated primarily through its emphasis on satisfying basic human needs (Büchs, 2021, p. 4; Coote, 2022, p. 474; Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 8⁴⁸; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 20⁴⁹). At its core, UBS is explicitly designed to ensure the collective or public provision of essential services that guarantee universal access to basic needs. Scholars argue that such decommodification of essential goods and services provides a more efficient and equitable means of needs satisfaction compared to market-based mechanisms (Büchs, 2021, p. 4⁵⁰). Moreover, UBS functions as a form of in-kind income, enhancing individuals' autonomy from paid employment by satisfying needs directly and contributing to greater time affluence – that is, the ability to enjoy more discretionary time for personal, social, or civic engagement (Büchs, 2021, p. 8).

The *ecological dimension* of UBS is captured succinctly in Coote's (2022) definition that basic services are “designed and delivered to promote and enable sufficiency within planetary boundaries” (p. 475). This ecological rationale rests on the principle that UBS facilitates collective consumption, which can be steered toward more resource-efficient and sustainable practices (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 15⁵¹; Coote, 2022, p. 475). Examples include prioritizing renewable energy use (Büchs, 2021, p. 5), investing in green infrastructure (Kapeller et al., 2023, p. 1), and strengthening local supply chains (McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 20⁵²). In addition, high-quality, publicly accessible spaces can encourage shared use and reduce the energy demand of private households (Carrosio & De Vidovich, 2023, p. 11), while comprehensive public transportation systems can decrease reliance on private car travel and thereby lower greenhouse gas emissions (Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 3).

⁴⁸ (O'Neill et al., 2018; Vogel & Hickel, 2023)

⁴⁹ (Coote & Percy, 2020)

⁵⁰ (Coote & Percy, 2020)

⁵¹ (Coote, 2021; Vogel et al., 2021)

⁵² (Sayer, 2019)

4.2.4. Wealth and Income Regulation Policies

Another eco-social policy category examined in moderate depth in the final sample concerns *wealth and income regulation policies*. This category primarily includes the two *semi-core proposals* of wealth regulation policies and income regulation policies, which are discussed in greater detail below.

Wealth Regulation Policies

Wealth regulation policies mostly refer to wealth taxation, which are levies on net wealth – defined as the total value of assets minus outstanding liabilities (Kapeller et al., 2023, p. 3). Kapeller et al. (2023) distinguish between three main variants of wealth regulation: flat-rate, progressive, and capped models (pp. 5–7). In most publications, however, the form of wealth regulation is not specified; authors refer more generally to the taxation of wealth as a policy instrument (Dukelow, 2022, p. 504; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 515; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 7). One exception is François et al. (2023, p. 2), who specifically focus and elaborate on wealth caps.

The *social dimension* of wealth regulation is explicitly linked to its redistributive potential. Wealth regulation is viewed as an instrument to reduce socio-economic inequality (N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 7; François et al., 2023, p. 1; Kapeller et al., 2023, p. 1). Beyond redistribution, several authors connect wealth regulation to the broader goal of fostering a post-growth economy (N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 7; François et al., 2023, p. 1). Since post-growth perspectives prioritize the satisfaction of basic needs within ecological limits, wealth regulation indirectly contributes to social objectives through this lens.

The *ecological dimension* of wealth regulation is twofold: first, wealth regulation is proposed as a means to target high-emission households, whose consumption patterns disproportionately drive carbon emissions (François et al., 2023, p. 2; Kapeller et al., 2023, p. 10⁵³). In this regard, wealth regulation overlaps conceptually with “eco-taxes” (Dukelow, 2022, p. 504), extending fiscal responsibility to those with the greatest environmental footprints. Second, similar to the social argument, the association between wealth regulation and a post-growth economy embeds an ecological rationale: by constraining excessive accumulation and promoting sufficiency, such regulation fosters the compliance with planetary boundaries (François et al., 2023, p. 2).

⁵³ (Chancel & Piketty, 2015; Oswald et al., 2020)

Income Regulation Policies

Alongside wealth regulation, *income regulation policies* represent another semi-core policy proposal. It particularly refers to the taxation of all forms of household income, including wages, self-employment earnings, pensions, social transfers, and capital income (François et al., 2023, p. 2⁵⁴). The literature distinguishes between several forms of income regulation, most notably progressive income taxation (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 515; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 7) and income caps, which establish a maximum permissible income level (François et al., 2023, p. 2; Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 3). François et al. (2023) provide a comprehensive overview of wealth and income regulation proposals discussed in both academic and policy circles. These proposals vary in their underlying motives (e.g., social transformation or inequality reduction), scope (wealth or income), level (the ratio between minimum and maximum income), target group (e.g., all individuals), policy instrument (taxation or command-and-control regulation), use of revenues (e.g., education or public debt reduction), and policy mix (e.g., combined with a UBI or carbon currency).

The *social dimension* of income regulation closely parallels that of wealth regulation. Its primary social objective is to reduce inequality by redistributing income within societies (N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 7; François et al., 2023, p. 2). In addition, some scholars argue that progressive income taxation can enhance perceived fairness by realigning the social valuation of different forms of labor (Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 10). A further, and repeating, link is the association between income caps and the promotion of a post-growth economy (François et al., 2023, p. 2).

The *ecological dimension* of income regulation, particularly in relation to income caps, mirrors that of wealth regulation. From an ecological perspective, such caps aim to limit excessive consumption by the highest-income groups – those whose carbon footprints are disproportionately large (François et al., 2023, p. 2). By constraining luxury consumption and reducing the demand for resource-intensive goods, income caps could contribute to lowering aggregate environmental pressures (Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 10).

4.2.5. Labor Market Policies

The final category of eco-social policy proposals concerns *labor market policies*. These policies aim to repurpose traditional labor market interventions and the associated public employment

⁵⁴ (Piketty, 2017; Roine & Waldenström, 2015)

services (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 513). Public employment services are government agencies that assist jobseekers in securing paid employment (Neier et al., 2024, p. 4). However, (eco-social) labor market policies broaden this scope by emphasizing eco-social work, defined as work that “enables individuals to pursue needs-oriented and environmentally friendly activities [...] and recognizes and includes unpaid forms of labor” (Neier et al., 2024, p. 4).

These labor market policies can be further differentiated into three subtypes: (a) labor guarantees, (b) eco-social retraining and qualification, and (c) eco-social information policies. Among these, the labor guarantee represents a semi-core policy proposal, while the latter two are discussed more peripherally.

Labor Guarantees

Labor guarantees are linked to labor within local communities and often contribute directly to ecological and social goals (Neier et al., 2024, p. 7; Dukelow, 2022, p. 504; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 514⁵⁵). They encompass both paid and unpaid activities and therefore go beyond the conventional job guarantee (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 514⁵⁶). The job guarantee – which ensures access to paid employment – is more frequently discussed in the literature (Dukelow, 2022, p. 503; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 8; Laksevic et al., 2025, p. 3), with some scholars further elaborating on green job guarantees (Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024, p. 7).

In terms of the *social dimension*, labor guarantees clearly align with social policy objectives. The primary rationale – particularly for job guarantees – is their capacity to prevent unemployment by ensuring access to work opportunities. This rationale recurs throughout the analyzed literature (Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024, p. 10; Dukelow, 2022, p. 503; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 8; Laksevic et al., 2025, p. 8).

Regarding *ecological objectives*, labor guarantees – especially when designed as green job guarantees – aim to strengthen environmentally sustainable industries. Such schemes would help mobilize a workforce for activities such as retrofitting buildings and installing renewable energy infrastructure (Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024, pp. 11–12; Dukelow, 2022, p. 503; Laksevic et al., 2025, p. 3⁵⁷). Moreover, these policies can facilitate a just transition by protecting workers in emission-intensive sectors affected by decarbonization processes (Laksevic et al., 2025, p. 7). This objective aligns with the broader notion of just transition labor market policies (Ding

⁵⁵ (Stamm et al., 2020; Swaton, 2018)

⁵⁶ (Claassen, 2018)

⁵⁷ (Alcott, 2013)

& Hirvilammi, 2024, p. 10). A weaker but noteworthy linkage to the ecological dimension is found in discussions connecting labor guarantees to post-growth transformations (Dukelow, 2022, p. 505).

Eco-Social Training and Qualification

Compared to labor guarantees, *eco-social training and qualification policies* receive less extensive coverage in the analyzed literature. These policies, also subsumed under the broader category of labor market policies, primarily aim to enhance green skills and competencies (Neier et al., 2024, p. 9; Theodoropoulou et al., 2024, p. 9). Concrete policy proposals include training programs in electrification (Bonetti & Villa, 2023, p. 476), community-service leave, which “would give employees the opportunity to work in social-ecological fields for a certain period without terminating their prior employment” (Neier et al., 2024, p. 11), retraining rights for workers in at-risk sectors (Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024, p. 8⁵⁸), work foundations that consist of state–industry collaborations providing skill development, and green skilled worker scholarships (Neier et al., 2024, p. 9).

In line with *social policy objectives*, eco-social retraining and qualification policies seek to secure employment opportunities and facilitate continued labor market participation, much like labor guarantees (Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024, p. 8). From an *ecological perspective*, they aim to prepare and motivate workers to transition from emission-intensive industries toward more sustainable sectors that contribute to decarbonization and green economic restructuring (Neier et al., 2024, p. 12; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 8; Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024, p. 10).

Eco-Social Information

A third and related subtype is *eco-social information*, which also falls under the umbrella of labor market policies. Eco-social information focuses on improving access to information about eco-social career pathways for both current and prospective members of the workforce (Neier et al., 2024, p. 3). Examples include eco-social job-trail maps provided by public employment services and eco-social work labels that identify socially and environmentally beneficial occupations (Neier et al., 2024, p. 8). By simultaneously advancing employment security and ecological sustainability (through jobs in green industries), eco-social information policies exhibit a clear dual alignment with both the *social* and *ecological dimensions*, thereby qualifying as eco-social policies.

⁵⁸ (Bohnenberger, 2022)

Summary

This chapter has reported on sample characteristics such as the final sample consisting predominantly of publications between 2022–2024 and being published in social-policy and sustainability-oriented journals. The qualitative content analysis, being guided by three sub-questions addressing prominent policy categories, individual proposals, and their associated ecological and social objectives, delivered the following: identification of the eco-social policy proposal categories “basic income policies”, “working-time policies”, “basic service policies”, “income and wealth regulation”, and “labor-market policies”. Scholarly attention is strongly concentrated on the first three categories, while labor-market policies remain comparatively underexplored. At the level of individual proposals, UBI, WTR, and UBS emerge as core reference points in the literature, complemented by a range of semi-core and peripheral proposals. The analysis further reveals substantial variation in how ecological and social objectives are articulated, ranging from explicit causal pathways to more implicit or indirect linkages, especially on the ecological dimension.

5. Discussion

This discussion begins with a concise summary of the key findings, followed by an assessment of the transformative potential of the identified eco-social policies in relation to sustainable welfare. It then turns to conceptual challenges within current eco-social policy scholarship, highlighting ongoing debates and proposing an extension of existing typological approaches. Finally, it considers the political-economic conditions under which eco-social policies may be adopted.

5.1. Summary of Findings

This thesis addressed the main research question: *Which eco-social policy proposals are discussed in contemporary academic literature within the sustainable welfare and eco-social policy research field?* Three sub-questions guided the analysis: (a) Which categories of eco-social policy proposals are most prominent? (b) Which individual proposals receive the most substantive attention? (c) Which ecological and social objectives are associated with these proposals and serve as the rationale for categorizing them as eco-social policy proposals?

First, the analysis identifies *five categories* of eco-social policy proposals that exhibit sufficient research density: basic income policies, working time policies, basic service policies, income and wealth regulation policies, and labor market policies. The literature is dominated by the first three, while income and wealth regulation policies receive considerably less scholarly attention and labor-market-oriented proposals are only marginally represented.

Second, the findings show that *specific policy proposals* have become focal points within the field. UBI, WTR, and UBS constitute the core proposals. Semi-core proposals include PI, various forms of income and wealth regulation (flat or progressive taxation, income or wealth caps), and labor guarantees. Peripheral proposals – such as eco-social vouchers, transition income, working time distribution measures (e.g., paternity leave, job-sharing arrangements), and eco-social retraining or information policies – receive notably less academic attention.

Third, the analysis reveals substantial variation in the *ecological* and *social objectives* attributed to eco-social policies. Some publications articulate clear and explicit causal pathways linking policy interventions to ecological or social outcomes, whereas others imply more indirect mechanisms, with ecological effects particularly likely to be discussed implicitly. The substance of these objectives also varies widely: social objectives range from broad basic needs satisfaction to more specific intended results such as enhanced autonomy from wage labor,

while ecological objectives range from concrete proposals for ecologically regenerative forms of work to broad commitments to respecting planetary boundaries.

Beyond the thematic findings, the analysis also examined the *characteristics* of the *final sample*. Across two major sources – the WoS and the EW database – 824 publications were initially identified. Applying inclusion and exclusion criteria reduced this pool to 101 relevant publications. Due to resource constraints, this set was further narrowed to 23 highly relevant publications, which constitute the final sample. A large majority of these publications appeared between 2022 and 2024, and roughly two-thirds were published in social-policy or sustainability-oriented journals. The majority of publications were indexed in both databases.

5.2. Transformative Potential of Eco-Social Policies

The findings illustrate the ecological and social objectives pursued by the identified *eco-social policy proposals*. This matters because eco-social policies, by definition, integrate ecological and social aims, while sustainable welfare specifies these aims more narrowly as the satisfaction of basic needs within planetary boundaries⁵⁹. Since the criteria for classifying a policy as eco-social are broader than those defining sustainable welfare, it seems fruitful relevant to examine whether the identified policies – based on their stated objectives and intended results – can contribute to the vision of sustainable welfare and thus demonstrate *transformative potential*. However, two aspects need to be emphasized: first, the transformative potential of eco-social policies depends highly on the temporal and spatial scope of the welfare system under consideration. Second, the focus of this thesis is not the evaluation of the transformative potential of eco-social policy proposals. Accordingly, the following discussion is intended to highlight selected points of debate rather than to provide a comprehensive assessment of the transformative potential of each policy.

Having this in mind, the discussion proceeds by briefly discussing how one concrete eco-social policy proposal of each of the five policy categories relates to (a) basic need satisfaction and (b) compliance with planetary boundaries.⁶⁰

UBI aligns strongly with sustainable welfare's emphasis on *basic need satisfaction*, as it provides income independent of paid employment (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 9; Büchs,

⁵⁹ See section “Sustainable Welfare”.

⁶⁰ Note that this section “Transformative Potential of Eco-Social Policy Proposals” builds largely upon the section “Qualitative Synthesis of Eco-Social Policy Proposals” and refers mostly to aforementioned publications of the final sample.

2021, p. 4; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 21⁶¹) and thereby contributes to the satisfaction of the intermediate need “economic security” and potentially also “adequate nutrition”, and “protective housing”. Satisfying those intermediate needs fosters the satisfaction of “autonomy”, which is a core basic (Gough, 1991, 170).⁶² However, its transformative potential is limited by the possibility that beneficiaries may use the income to pursue preference-driven or conspicuous consumption, rather than need-oriented consumption (Goldsmith, 2010, p. 10) – particularly because the UBI contains no mechanism to steer spending toward sufficiency. This risk is amplified by the broader alignment of reigning preference satisfaction theory and neoliberalism, both of which rely on market choices as expressions of individual desire (Daly & Farley, 2011; Heathwood, 2014).⁶³

From a Marxist political economy perspective, the UBI has been characterized as potentially functioning as a “trojan horse” (Hogg, 2023, p. 143). Historically, the policy has been supported by actors with neoliberal or regressive agendas, including the “socially conscious billionaire” (Zizek, 2015, p. 39) such as Mark Zuckerberg and Elon Musk (Hogg, 2023, p. 145). When paired with automation, the UBI may enable firms to reduce labor demand, externalizing wage costs to the public while increasing profits (Hogg, 2023, p. 145–146). Yet a Marxist perspective also identifies countervailing emancipatory effects, arguing that the UBI could strengthen workers’ bargaining power by ensuring basic need satisfaction independent of the labor market, by raising aggregate demand when funded progressively, and by expanding political and associative capacities through increased free time (Manjarin & Szlinder, 2016).

UBS similarly focuses on satisfying basic needs by providing public, decommodified services (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 10; Büchs, 2021, p. 1; Coote, 2022, p. 474; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022b, p. 511; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022; Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 8; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 20). In contrast to the market-mediated UBI, *UBS* shifts access to goods and services to state and non-state providers, with government functioning as a facilitator (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022, p. 511⁶⁴). Critics raise concerns about bureaucratic inefficiency and whether standardized services can adequately meet diverse needs (Büchs, 2021, p. 4). However, *UBS* frameworks typically rely on democratic and participatory processes – such as citizen forums – to define and operationalize needs (Büchs, 2021, p. 4; Lindellee et al., 2021, p. 330). Like the UBI, *UBS* may reduce the minimum (wage labor) income required for a decent life and thereby

⁶¹ (Parijs, 1995)

⁶² See subsection “Satisfaction of Basic Needs”.

⁶³ See subsection “Satisfaction of Basic Needs”.

⁶⁴ (Coote & Percy, 2020)

enhance autonomy (Büchs, 2021, p. 8). The extent to which UBS fulfills specific needs (e.g., adequate nutrition, protective housing, safe environments) depends on the design of the service portfolio (Coote, 2022, p. 476).

WTR similarly shows transformative potential by potentially enhancing temporal autonomy, improving health outcomes, and potentially supporting meaningful social relationships through increased time prosperity (Hanbury et al., 2023, p. 8). These features directly contribute to basic need satisfaction as defined in sustainable welfare. By contrast, income regulation's transformative potential in the social dimension is unclear. While it reduces socioeconomic inequality – a necessary condition for sustainable welfare (Büchs, 2021, p. 3; Hirvilammi, 2020, p. 9) – its primary social effect tends to concern distributive fairness rather than direct basic need satisfaction (Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 10). Similarly labor guarantee's transformative potential is unclear based upon the findings: although preventing unemployment may contribute indirectly to economic security (Dukelow, 2022, p. 503; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 8; Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 3), it is unclear how it substantively transforms conditions of basic need satisfaction.

Sustainable welfare also requires *compliance with planetary boundaries*. The question is the extent to which the identified eco-social policies exhibit transformative potential in their intended ecological effects.

UBI's ecological objectives are discussed only implicitly in the sample and rely largely on expected consumption and labor-supply effects. While reduced material throughput via less materially-intensive consumption (Büchs, 2021, p. 5) or via less aggregate employment (Büchs, 2021, p. 8; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 21⁶⁵) could reduce pressures on planetary boundaries, these outcomes remain uncertain.⁶⁶

In contrast, *UBS* indicates more transformative potential in the ecological dimension. Because provision is designed around needs, UBS inherently prioritizes sufficiency and limits unnecessary material and energy throughput (Coote 2022, p. 475). Collective consumption patterns can be directed toward sufficient rather than excessive consumption, while needs-oriented services can integrate efficiency and consistency strategies – for example, by relying

⁶⁵ (McKay, 2011)

⁶⁶ A comprehensive overview of ecological effects of basic incomes can be found in Howard et al. (2023).

on renewable energy and local supply chains (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 15⁶⁷; Büchs, 2021, p. 5; Coote, 2022, p. 475; Kapeller et al., 2023, p. 1; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 20⁶⁸).

The ecological sustainable welfare potential of *WTR* depends heavily on income and time effects. If wages are not compensated, reduced income may translate into reduced consumption aligned with less income to spend on products (Persson et al., 2022, p. 84; Hanbury et al., 2023, p. 8; Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 12⁶⁹). The time effect presumes that individuals will engage in less environmentally intensive activities, which remains contested (Persson et al., 2022, p. 84; Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 6). Similar to UBI, *WTR* may reduce aggregate employment and thereby potentially reduce economic output (Hanbury et al., 2023, p. 7; Jenny et al., 2024, p. 5).⁷⁰

Income regulation may exhibit comparatively higher ecological transformative potential because the highest-income groups have the largest environmental footprints (François et al., 2023, p. 2). Reducing the disposable income of the richest deciles could impose forms of “forced sufficiency,” decreasing pressures on climate and land systems (Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 10). However, the effectiveness of such regulation in altering high-income consumption patterns depends on design. More stringent mechanisms, such as income and wealth caps, may have stronger potential to reduce environmentally intensive consumption, since “reliance on voluntary actions by the wealthy will not suffice” (Bohnenberger, 2025, p. 36).

The *labor guarantee* may also possess ecological transformative potential if designed as a green labor market guarantee – for example, by creating jobs in retrofitting buildings or installing renewable energy systems (Ding & Hirvilammi, 2024, pp. 11–12; Dukelow, 2022, p. 503; Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 3⁷¹). In such cases, it could directly contribute to climate mitigation. Designed as basic labor guarantee, ecological gains from this policy proposal remain up to discussion.

Some *limitations* of discussing the transformative potential but also generally eco-social effects of eco-social policies need to be pointed out: one major limitation is the gap between policy objectives and actual policy effects – whether these objectives translate into real-world effects partially remains uncertain. For instance, UBI analysis is restricted to researching effects of

⁶⁷ (Coote, 2021; Vogel et al., 2021)

⁶⁸ (Sayer, 2019)

⁶⁹ (Schor, 2005)

⁷⁰ Various studies over the last years have contributed to potential ecological effects of *WTR* (Antal et al., 2020; Cieplinski et al., 2021; King & van den Bergh, 2017).

⁷¹ (Alcott, 2013)

partial or experimental basic income policies, since it has not been introduced in a substantive scale (Gibson et al., 2018; Watkins, 2025). This limits validity of research aiming to contribute to UBI's effects. Adding upon that eco-social policy analysis is further restricted, since such analysis requires a conceptually clear definition of eco-social policy. Yet what constitutes an eco-social policy remains contested within current scholarship (Laruffa, 2024; Mandelli, 2022; Schulze Waltrup, 2025a), a debate taken up in the subsequent part of the discussion chapter.

5.3. Conceptual Issues of Eco-Social Policy

The following section offers a *critical examination* of both theoretical and practical *conceptualizations of eco-social policies*. Its purpose is not to challenge the legitimacy of the broader research field on eco-social policy and sustainable welfare, but rather to enhance conceptual clarity and precision, thereby contributing to a stronger analytical foundation for future research. This discussion section covers key limitations in current influential conceptualizations – issues that became particularly apparent during this research – and proposes alternative directions to advance the field.

Before critically engaging with the field's eco-social policy concepts, it is important to recall that this research employs Mandelli's (2022) typology. This framework emphasizes integrated ecological and social objectives rather than primarily economic growth goals and distinguishes (a) explicit, output-based and non-normative eco-social policies from (b) implicit, outcome-based and normative eco-social policies. For the purposes of this study, a broad interpretation of the implicitness criterion was adopted, which aligns with the research objectives.⁷²

Implicit, output-based and normative eco-social policy approaches *dominate* field scholarship (Mandelli, 2022, p. 340), with implicitness criteria gaining increasing academic prominence. Recent research demonstrates this trend through increasingly elaborate implicit typologies and strengthened arguments favoring outcome-based over output-based definitions: Schulze Waltrup (2025a) introduces an implicit eco-social policy typology structured around four perspectives: Green Economy, Green Keynesianism, Recomposing Consumption and Production, and Degrowth. The “Green Economy” and “Green Keynesian” perspectives both adopt green growth orientations, with the former emphasizing private sector leadership in social-ecological transformation while the latter pointing to the “entrepreneurial state” (Mazzucato, 2023). The “Recomposing Consumption and Production” perspective proves more transformative than green growth approaches, adopting growth-agnostic positions while

⁷² See section “Methodology: Systematic Literature Review”.

pursuing resource consumption redistribution through mechanisms including consumption corridors. Finally, the “Degrowth” perspective embraces radical transformation by abandoning growth imperatives entirely, envisioning “a completely different way of organising society” (Schulze Waltrup, 2025a, p. 28). Essentially, the typology prioritizes policies’ relationship with economic growth (economic dimension) over integrated ecological-social objectives. By emphasizing eco-social policies’ potential for facilitating social change – specifically, indirect policy outcomes and impacts – this framework exemplifies implicit conceptualization.

Laruffa (2024) significantly influences recent *definitional discourse* by advocating implicit eco-social policy concepts from critical, emancipatory perspectives. He challenges both Mandelli’s (2022) typological framework and pronounced preference for explicit approaches.

Laruffa’s (2024) *critique* targets the normative/non-normative distinction central to Mandelli’s (2022) typology, wherein Mandelli attributes normativity to implicit approaches while claiming non-normativity for explicit definitions. Laruffa (2024) contests this dichotomy, arguing that while implicit policies (UBI, UBS and WTR) possess normative dimensions, explicit definitions prove equally normative by reinforcing capitalist growth paradigms’ status quo. Furthermore, he argues that normative eco-social policy definitions allow scholars to set a standard for evaluating implemented policies (Laruffa, 2024, p. 9–11).

Laruffa proceeds from the premise that social policy discourse extends beyond scientific arenas, generating political consequences that either facilitate or impede emancipatory transformation. Consequently, Laruffa (2024, pp. 3, 5) positions policies’ relationships with economic growth as the decisive classificatory criterion – thereby simultaneously subordinating integrated eco-social objectives (paradoxically, given the “eco-social” terminology) while advancing implicit, outcome- (or impact-based) conceptualizations.

Elaborating this position, Laruffa (2024) builds upon Schulze Waltrup’s (2025a) typology to distinguish green growth-promoting eco-social policies from post-growth-oriented alternatives. Laruffa (2024) rejects green growth approaches as non-emancipatory, arguing they advance ecological modernization projects that preserve imperial mode of living (Brand & Wissen, 2017, 2024, pp. 93–96) and capitalist expansion through what Nancy Fraser (2023) terms “cannibal capitalism” – consuming ever more social and ecological domains. Conversely, Laruffa (2024) contends eco-social policy must embrace growth critique and enable radical transformation, aligning with eco-social policies’ instrumental role in facilitating sustainable welfare.

This positioning explicitly situates eco-social policies within post-growth research (Laruffa, 2024, p. 5) – an unsurprising development given the field’s established post-growth affinities (Büchs, 2025, p. 169; Hirvilammi & Koch, 2020, p. 2; Koch & Mont, 2016b, pp. 203–204; Mandelli, 2022, p. 339). While Laruffa’s (2024) growth-critical conception proves conceptually compelling as an implicit, outcome-based approach, several aspects warrant *critical examination*:

First, Laruffa’s (2024) implicit, emancipatory eco-social policies raise questions about distinctiveness from post-growth policy proposals. Post-growth scholarship advocates reducing growth imperatives’ hegemonic status while prioritizing human wellbeing enhancement within planetary boundaries (Kallis et al., 2025, p. e62). Systematic post-growth policy reviews by Cosme et al. (2017) and N. Fitzpatrick et al. (2022) encompass both state-led and private sector interventions, with state policies demonstrating substantial overlap – indeed, near-identity – with eco-social policies identified in this research. Research intensity patterns prove remarkably similar: N. Fitzpatrick et al. (2022) identify UBI, WTR, job guarantees, and income caps as receiving highest scholarly attention, covering all policy proposal categories except basic services (e.g., UBS).

Laruffa’s (2024) emancipatory, growth-critical eco-social policies could reasonably constitute a post-growth policy subset – or vice versa. Moreover, Laruffa’s (2024) framework aligns more closely with sustainable welfare paradigms, which themselves parallel post-growth visions – differing primarily in entry points rather than substantive content: sustainable welfare approaches via social policy perspectives (Mandelli, 2022, p. 339) while post-growth primarily enters through ecological economics framings (Kallis et al., 2025, p. e62). These convergences suggest productive potential for enhanced coordination and collaboration between eco-social policy sustainable welfare, and post-growth research communities. Strategically, such resource consolidation could amplify both fields’ contributions toward shared objectives: facilitating social-ecological transformation.

Second, emancipatory, implicit eco-social policy classification presents substantial difficulties – issues Mandelli (2022) identified that remain pertinent for Laruffa’s (2024) and Schulze Waltrup’s (2025a) approaches. These classification challenges emerged prominently in this research, with findings demonstrating how policies acquire eco-social status through implicit intended outcomes.

UBI exemplifies these difficulties. At heart, UBI possesses relatively direct social objectives: ensuring sufficient, unconditional income enabling market-based needs satisfaction through

consumption of goods and services (Büchs, 2021, pp. 1–2). However, ecological rationales prove comparatively indirect and less convincing: cash transfers may reduce working hours, increasing recipients’ time autonomy and enabling shifts toward activities and consumption patterns meeting genuine needs – which theoretically exhibit lower material intensity than previous consumption forms (Büchs, 2021, p. 8; Langridge, 2024, p. 3; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 21⁷³). Ecological effects thus constitute potential downstream outcomes positioned at causal chains’ endpoints, while social objectives represent immediate outputs at causal origins.⁷⁴ Social objectives appear substantially more plausible and realistic than distant ecological outcomes, raising questions about UBI’s classification: does eco-social policy designation prove convincing, or should UBI remain categorized as social policy?

WTR demonstrates parallel classification ambiguities. WTR establishes direct social objectives – increasing free time and temporal prosperity (Hanbury et al., 2023, p. 8) – while ecological rationales posit that additional free time enables less environmentally intensive activities including slow mobility adoption activities (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 13⁷⁵; Persson et al., 2022, p. 84; Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 6). Ecological objectives constitute distant outcomes dependent upon social output realization. Again, classification questions arise: does WTR warrant eco-social designation, or would social policy categorization prove conceptually clearer?

UBI and WTR exemplify implicit *definitions’ vagueness*, prompting questions about implicit approaches’ value if they risk diluting eco-social policy concepts. Implicit eco-social policies’ validity remains contested – concerns Mandelli (2022, p. 340) previously articulated. Mandelli (2022) advocates explicit, output-based definitions as preferable pathways forward. Notably, even Laruffa (2024, p. 7) acknowledges that Mandelli’s (2022) definition “has become rapidly influential in the field [...] and it is likely to become a point of reference in the literature.”

However, while Mandelli’s (2022) explicit approach may enhance conceptual clarity, the implicit-output-based-green-growth versus implicit-outcome-based-post-growth eco-social policy debate proves misleading – due to the *absent of coherent causal logics* in the debate. Conceptual clarity could be enhanced by (a) deeper exploration of relationships between policy objectives and actual effects, informing realistic causal chains, and (b) integrating theory of change concepts into eco-social policy typologies.

⁷³ (McKay, 2011)

⁷⁴ See section “Qualitative Synthesis of Eco-Social Policy Proposals”.

⁷⁵ (Knight et al., 2013)

Regarding *objective-effect relationships*, policy evaluation research could foster realistic causal chains. Current definitions tend to employ policy objective criteria rather than actual effect criteria – meaning policies acquire eco-social status through possessing eco-social objectives regardless of whether implementation achieves those objectives. However, policy evaluation demonstrating objective non-attainment could necessitate objective reformulation, potentially removing eco-social classification. UBI exemplifies this scenario: currently argued as eco-social, evaluation research might demonstrate UBI lacks positive ecological effects⁷⁶ – leading not to reduced resource-intensive consumption but rather increased material consumption due to enhanced disposable income. Such evaluation could inform UBI’s theory of change, potentially resulting in reclassification as social rather than eco-social policy – even under implicit, outcome-based criteria.

Integrating *theory of change* concepts into eco-social policy typologies could extend and clarify Mandelli’s (2022) framework. While Mandelli (2022) employs output and outcome terminology, he does not explicitly incorporate theory of change concepts, creating difficulties distinguishing (a) explicit, output-based from (b) implicit, outcome-based from (c) impact-based eco-social objectives. Furthermore, Mandelli’s (2022) framework inadequately addresses scenarios where single policies possess social objectives at output levels while ecological objectives emerge at outcome levels, or vice versa. Figure 9 “Theory of Change for Eco-Social Policy” presents a proposed alternative framework addressing these limitations:

Figure 9: Theory of Change for Eco-Social Policy; own figure

Theories of change, placed in the field of evaluation, enjoy widespread prominence such as in sustainable business (Andersson, 2024), artificial intelligence (Leeuw, 2024) and policy

⁷⁶ Acknowledging that evaluation of UBI is difficult, since research is limited to basic income experiments and small scale implementations (Watkins, 2025). See section “Transformative Potential of Eco-Social Policy Proposals”.

analysis (Levine, 2024). Being logic models, theories of change establish causality between inputs and subsequent intended results (Delahais, 2024, p. 17).⁷⁷

Applied to eco-social policy contexts, the theory of change posits that individual policy interventions generate outputs (first-level intended effects) of ecological and/or social nature. These outputs ideally progress toward particular social and/or ecological outcomes (second-level intended effects). Outcomes may subsequently produce ecological and/or social impacts (third-level intended effects).⁷⁸

Differentiating ecological and social dimensions across these three levels enables various integration quality combinations, yielding the typology presented in Figure 10 “Eco-Social Policy Typology”.

Eco-Social Policy Typology	Dimension	Objectives	
		Outputs	Outcomes
Strong eco-social policy	social	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	ecological	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Environmentally-extended social policy	social	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	ecological		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Socially-extended environmental policy	social		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	ecological	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
No eco-social policy	social		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	ecological		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 10: Eco-Social Policy Typology; own figure

The *typology* distinguishes four policy types: (a) strong eco-social policies possessing both ecological and social objectives at output levels (first + first level combination); (b) environmentally extended social policies (weak eco-social policies) featuring social outputs and outcomes alongside only ecological outcomes, lacking ecological outputs (second + first combination); (c) socially extended environmental policies (weak eco-social policies) featuring ecological outputs and outcomes alongside only social outcomes, lacking social outputs (first + second combination); and (d) non-eco-social policies lacking both ecological and social output objectives, possessing instead economic outputs or exclusively outcome-level ecological/social objectives (second + second, second + none, or none + second combinations).³

The *UBI* exemplifies an *environmentally extended social policy* – a weak eco-social policy – as illustrated in Figure 11 “Theory of change – Universal Basic Income”. At the first level, income

⁷⁷ See subsection “Public Policy”.

⁷⁸ See subsection “Public Policy”.

security for recipients constitutes a social output, while ecological output remains absent. At the second level, both social and ecological intended outcomes emerge. Social outcomes include recipients leveraging enhanced wage labor autonomy to reduce working time toward part-time arrangements and redirect gained leisure toward common good activities. Ecological outcomes involve recipients shifting from conspicuous consumption patterns toward activities meeting genuine needs with lower material intensity, thereby reducing aggregate material throughput. At the third level, reduced material throughput potentially alleviates pressure on the “land-system change” planetary boundary, enhancing planetary boundary compliance, while recipients’ increased leisure and common good engagement potentially satisfy the basic need for autonomy, contributing toward “minimally impaired social participation” (Gough, 2017, p. 43). UBI’s effects demonstrate causal interdependency and mutual reinforcement. Theory of change frameworks help structure and visualize these causal pathways, demonstrating this analytical approach’s potential value for eco-social policy scholarship.

Figure 11: Theory of Change – Universal Basic Income; own figure

These considerations suggest three *research directions*: (a) employing theory of change frameworks when analyzing institutionally adopted eco-social policies; (b) conducting systematic literature reviews applying the proposed eco-social policy typology; and (c) expanding policy evaluation research on implemented eco-social policies to validate theories of change and inform coherent output, outcome, and impact specification.

Weak eco-social policies possess limited transformative potential compared to strong eco-social policies’ substantial capacities for advancing sustainable welfare.⁷⁹ From socio-ecological transformation perspectives, higher-potential policies prove normatively preferable, suggesting

⁷⁹ “Transformative potential” in this thesis denotes policies’ capacity for advancing sustainable welfare – specifically, basic needs satisfaction (social dimension) within planetary boundaries (ecological dimension). This conceptualization differs from Laruffa’s (2024) and Schulze Waltrup’s (2025) frameworks, which prioritize economic dimensions, defining transformative potential primarily through post-growth economy establishment. While this thesis adopts distinct definitional parameters, economic dimensions’ influence on ecological and social outcomes remains acknowledged, as demonstrated through ecological and socio-economic growth critiques (see section “Sustainable Welfare”).

research should prioritize developing strong eco-social interventions. However, critical examination raises questions about designing singular policies with high transformative potential: can individual policies function as “*eco-social panaceas*”, and should research prioritize such comprehensive singular interventions over alternative approaches?

N. Fitzpatrick et al. (2022) caution against such focus on isolated solutions, since “policies are never implemented in isolation, it would be naïve for anyone aspiring for systemic change to focus policy-making efforts on one silver bullet policy” (p. 9). By that they point to an alternative approach – more beneficial from both normative and research perspectives – involves shifting from singular policies toward *eco-social policy packages*. This shift might offer dual advantages:

First, policy packages enhance *conceptual clarity* – rather than struggling with singular eco-social policy identification, researchers can leverage established environmental and social policy domains’ conceptual frameworks, identifying policies within these domains and subsequently combining them into packages.

Second, policy packages enable designing *strong eco-social combinations* possessing high transformative potential. Such packages might combine individual environmental and social policies: environmental policies contribute ecological objectives at output levels while social policies contribute social objectives at output levels, potentially amplifying eco-social potential depending on synergistic interactions.

Scholars broadly *recognize the necessity* of researching and designing comprehensive policy packages – multiple mutually reinforcing policies facilitating socio-ecological transformation (Dukelow & Murphy, 2022b, p. 514; François et al., 2023, p. 1; Fritz & Eversberg, 2023, p. 496; Laruffa et al., 2022, p. 509). While eco-social policy packages do not constitute this research’s primary focus, 15 of 23 sampled publications address them with varying analytical depth – from brief mentions to elaborate discussions (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023; Büchs, 2021; Coote, 2022; Dukelow, 2022; Dukelow & Murphy, 2022b; N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022; François et al., 2023; Jenny et al., 2024; Kapeller et al., 2023; Lage, 2025; Laksevics et al., 2025; Langridge, 2024; Laruffa et al., 2022; McGann & Murphy, 2023; Neier et al., 2024).

For instance, Büchs’ (2021) publication on a *UBI-UBS combination* shows particular depth. While some scholars argue these policies generate crowding-out effects (Coote & Percy, 2020, p. 51), Büchs (2021) contends they function synergistically when designed as integrated packages. From UBI perspectives, if basic services provide sufficient water and electricity

freely, required UBI levels decrease for satisfying other necessities. From UBS perspectives, if UBI enables common good activity engagement, recipients participate more effectively in bottom-up design and provision processes for basic goods and services (Büchs, 2021, p. 2). Public opinion partially supports this combination (Laksevics et al., 2025, p. 9). However, precise package design mechanisms remain contested, particularly regarding domains prioritizing individual preferences (e.g., food, clothing) versus collective provisioning (e.g., mobility) (Büchs, 2021, p. 7).

Some publications in the final sample also cover *WTR packages*. For instance, WTR paired with job guarantees could redirect productivity gains toward reduced working hours rather than increased production (N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022, p. 8). WTR with wage reductions may combine with basic income policies (PI and UBI) and UBS to further decouple livelihood security from wage labor dependency (Bärnthaler & Dengler, 2023, p. 13). Some proposals extend to three-policy packages combining UBI, WTR, and job guarantees (Dukelow, 2022, p. 503).

These examples constitute weak eco-social policy packages, combining two social policies. Future research could prioritize *strong eco-social policy packages* – combining environmental and social policies to generate ecological and social objectives at output levels. Examples include UBS (improved public transit and cycling infrastructure) paired with petrol vehicle bans (Jenny et al., 2024, p. 10), wealth taxation financing green European investments (Kapeller et al., 2023, p. 2), and carbon fee-and-dividend schemes (Bachler et al., 2024; Klenert et al., 2018). In more detail, carbon fee-and-dividend schemes intentionally combine environmental policy (carbon pricing to reduce emissions) and social policy (revenue redistribution / basic income to low-income households or affected regions) (Klenert et al., 2018a, p. 675; Krause, 2021, p. 332).

However, even if eco-social policy packages possess stronger transformative potential than singular policies, questions arise about whether policies alone can fulfill transformation expectations absent systemic changes. Reality demonstrates that *ceteris paribus* conditions rarely obtain; *public policies* represent merely *one strategy* among multiple approaches required for social-ecological transformation (Wright, 2020). Wright (2020) distinguishes three transformation strategies: interstitial strategies fostering change through initiatives within

existing system niches, ruptural strategies targeting system breakdown and reconstruction, and symbiotic strategies pursuing incremental reform.⁸⁰

Eco-social policies and packages constitute *symbiotic strategies*.⁸¹ This classification points to the political implementation likelihood: do eco-social policies transcend theoretical discourse to achieve *practical realization*? This question proves particularly salient given the field's foundational connections to sustainability and transformation research traditions, which pursue not only scientific advancement but also actual societal (Schneidewind & Singer-Brodowski, 2014; Wittmayer et al., 2018).

5.4. Eco-Social Policy Implementation

While eco-social policies and policy packages exhibit significant transformative potential, their feasibility under current political and economic conditions remains uncertain. Translating these policies from theory to practice – such as the implementation of UBI, UBS, or WTR – faces several challenges. These challenges arise particularly from *macro-level structural constraints* and *dependencies*.

Eco-social policy implementation confronts challenging political-economic terrain. Critical questions concern state capacity and governmental willingness to adopt eco-social interventions. A decisive factor involves policies' *relationship* to economic *growth imperatives* – specifically, whether policies undermine or align with prevailing growth paradigms. Scholars including Gough (2022), Schulze Waltrup (2025a), and Laruffa (2024) have extensively conceptualized this typology.

Gough (2022, p. 469) provides the most concrete *policy categorization*: green growth-compatible policies include UBS, labor guarantees emphasizing foundational economy employment, fair wages, and guaranteed minimum income – with UBS and labor guarantees appearing prominently in contemporary research according to this study's findings. Post-growth-oriented policies encompass WTR, fair pay ratios, reduced financial and rentier job sectors, income and wealth caps, progressive taxation, advertising restrictions, and luxury consumption disincentives – with WTR and income/wealth caps remaining prominent in current scholarship per this study's findings.

⁸⁰ Wright (2020) emphasizes that effective transformation requires strategy combinations, integrating symbiotic, interstitial, and ruptural approaches (pp. 417–418).

⁸¹ Similar to Wright (2020), Schmelzer (2022) identifies an “institution-oriented current” within post-growth research – a current that emphasizes state reform and sufficiency policies (pp. 181–182).

Green growth-compatible eco-social policies demonstrate *higher political implementation likelihood*. In the German federal election in 2021, manifestos across all but one party acknowledged synergy potential between ecological and social objectives, though grounded in shared pro-growth assumptions. Partisan differences emerge in policy design specifics – with center-left and left-wing parties showing more coherence with sustainable welfare by emphasizing state involvement, welfare benefits, and needs-oriented interventions (T. Fischer & Giuliani, 2025, pp. 16–17).

Additionally, some eco-social policies gain political traction through alignment with *geopolitical rationales* beyond environmental and social rationales. Within the context of geopolitical tensions with Russia and subsequent stop of fossil gas imports to Germany, German Free Democratic Party Finance Minister Lindner framed renewable energy as “Freiheitsenergien” (freedom energies), adding national security justification for renewable expansion (RedaktionsNetzwerkDeutschland, 2022). However, this reframing potentially reverts to narrow energy security definitions prioritizing supply concerns over environmental sustainability considerations.⁸²

Conversely, eco-social policies potentially *undermining growth* face substantial implementation barriers, as states themselves remain fundamentally growth-dependent (Gumbert et al., 2022; Hausknost, 2019; Janischewski et al., 2024; Keyßer et al., 2025; C. C. Walker et al., 2021, 2024). Even though further research is needed on the nature of growth dependencies and the conditions under which they might be dismantled (Bohnenberger, 2023, p. 335), existing research already highlights the depth of these constraints. C. C. Walker et al. (2021), for example, conceptualize welfare states as being locked into multiple *growth-related dilemmas* that operate simultaneously at the micro-, meso-, and macro-levels of economic and social systems. They identify five interrelated challenges that together illustrate how strongly contemporary welfare states remain dependent on continued economic growth:

First, the *fiscal dilemma* concerns welfare state financing under zero or negative growth conditions. *Ceteris paribus*, governments receive reduced tax revenues when economic activity contracts (C. C. Walker et al., 2021, p. 5). This vulnerability stems from contemporary tax structures’ heavy dependence on economic activity-generated revenues measured through GDP (Büchs, 2021, p. 2). Economic growth thus finances welfare states, ensuring fiscal sustainability (D. Bailey, 2015; Hirvilammi, 2020, p. 12).

⁸² See subsection “Environmental Policy”.

Second, the *cost disease dilemma* addresses escalating relative welfare costs compared to other sectors – Baumol’s cost disease phenomenon (Strunz & Schindler, 2018, p. 72; C. C. Walker et al., 2021, p. 5). Low-productivity, labor-intensive sectors – such as healthcare and eldercare – tend to become increasingly costly relative to high-productivity, capital-intensive sectors that can benefit from mechanization (Baumol, 2017). However, Bailey et al. (2016) challenge the conventional interpretation of Baumol’s cost disease in the context of public services. They argue that the technological stagnation assumed by the Baumolian framework is overstated and that productivity-enhancing technological progress in public services is more feasible than commonly assumed.

Third, the *internal growth dependency dilemma* identifies growth imperatives embedded within welfare systems themselves, particularly healthcare (C. C. Walker et al., 2024). Healthcare systems operate under intervention-maximizing logics (Bauman, 2012, p. 79; Hensher & Zywert, 2020), disregarding both environmental footprints – failing to assess whether marginal welfare benefits justify substantial resource and energy consumption (C. C. Walker et al., 2021, p. 7; Zywert & Quilley, 2018, p. 202) – and genuine wellbeing enhancement, instead prioritizing financial performance metrics (M. Fischer, 2016, p. 5; C. C. Walker et al., 2021, p. 6).

Fourth, the *demand-resource mismatch dilemma* juxtaposes escalating welfare needs against finite resources. Growing and aging populations intensify welfare demand while dominant subjective wellbeing theories conceptualize “needs” as unlimited “desires” (C. C. Walker et al., 2021, p. 6),⁸³ creating inherently unsustainable dynamics.

Fifth, the *political transformation dilemma* concerns barriers preventing welfare state transformation toward growth independence. Most post-growth policy proposals – including UBI, WTR, and labor guarantees – require top-down implementation (Cosme et al., 2017). And political actors remain bound by layered state imperatives: foundational capital accumulation overlaid with legitimacy imperatives responding to working-class struggles (Hausknost, 2019, pp. 17, 20). Hausknost (2019) terms this the “glass ceiling of transformation,” precluding post-growth eco-social policy adoption. Collectively, these dependencies constitute the “Hegemony of Growth” (Schmelzer, 2016), obstructing emancipatory or post-growth eco-social policies (Laruffa, 2024).

Eco-social policies – whether aligned with green-growth or post-growth paradigms – face the risk of *political marginalization* due to the intensifying “green backlash,” defined as growing

⁸³ See subsection “Satisfaction of Basic Needs”.

societal and political opposition to climate transitions (Bosetti et al., 2025). This backlash is closely linked to the rising prominence of right-wing parties in governments and parliaments. A prominent illustration is Donald Trump’s first presidential term, during which the United States withdrew from the Paris Agreement, Obama-era Climate Action Plans were dismantled, the Environmental Protection Agency was defunded, and restrictions on oil and gas extraction were weakened (Bosetti et al., 2025, p. 82). Empirical studies show that right-wing parties constitute the only party family indicating more opposition to climate protection (Schwörer & Fernández-García, 2024). Their political narratives also pit social and ecological objectives against each other. For example, the German far-right party “Alternative für Deutschland” rejects the idea that environmental and social goals can generate mutual benefits (T. Fischer & Giuliani, 2025), while Donald Trump’s 2016 “Bring back coal” campaign slogan similarly framed decarbonization as socially harmful (Bosetti et al., 2025, p. 824).

Setting aside the wider political backlash, the question remains whether the eco-social policies identified in this study can help reduce welfare states’ structural growth dependencies or whether they risk reinforcing them. Several aspects speak to this issue:

Regarding the *funding dilemma*, some policies appear capable of easing the dependence of welfare states on economic growth. Shifting the tax base away from economic activity and toward immovable assets such as land and property can reduce reliance on growth-linked revenues (Bailey, 2015, p. 801) and aligns with wealth- and income-focused policy proposals. Wealth caps have been highlighted in this respect: beyond generating public revenue, they constrain excessive capital accumulation (Buch-Hansen & Koch, 2019, p. 14; Koch, 2022, p. 455). WTR may similarly lower growth pressures by facilitating full employment even under conditions of economic contraction, provided that job-sharing is institutionally supported (Petschow et al., 2018, pp. 124–125). By contrast, a UBI may reinforce growth dependencies when financed primarily through income or consumption taxes, both of which rely on economic activity (Petschow et al., 2018, pp. 147–148).

With respect to the *relative cost dilemma*, basic service policies – especially labor-intensive services – might increase the relative cost burden due to structurally low productivity growth. Bailey et al. (2016, p. 91), however, challenge this assumption by highlighting the potential for productivity gains through technological innovation, including telecare for older adults, automated or self-service public facilities, and digitalized policing.

Turning to the *internal dilemma*, C. C. Walker et al. (2024) argue that de-commodifying adult social care in the United Kingdom – akin to implementing UBS – can reduce growth

dependencies by removing opportunities for rent-seeking and diminishing the profit-driven logic of service delivery. They emphasize that provision could be shared across social enterprises, voluntary organizations, and public agencies (C. C. Walker et al., 2024, p. 8).

The *demand dilemma* presents competing perspectives: while some scholars propose extending working lives to stabilize pension systems under demographic aging (Grimm et al., 2024, pp. 144–145; Petschow et al., 2018, p. 132), this approach conflicts with working time policies aimed at reducing or redistributing working hours. C. C. Walker et al. (2021, p. 7) instead suggest that alternative welfare conceptions grounded in human-needs theory may reduce growth pressures. Building on this, UBI and UBS – both oriented toward securing human needs rather than maximizing market income (Büchs, 2021, pp. 1–2, 4; Coote, 2022, p. 474; Laksevic et al., 2025, p. 8⁸⁴; McGann & Murphy, 2023, p. 20⁸⁵) – may help alleviate demand-side growth dependencies: UBS in particular, when co-designed through bottom-up participatory processes, could redefine both the type and quantity of welfare provision regarded as necessary, potentially shifting social values toward sufficiency (Büchs, 2021, p. 4; Lindellee et al., 2021, p. 330). Preventative social policies that improve health and wellbeing may also mitigate demand pressures (C. C. Walker, 2024, p. 8). In this respect, WTR – associated with positive health outcomes – and UBI – aiming to enhance leisure time and income security – may offer additional benefits.⁸⁶

Concerning the *political dilemma*, several eco-social policy proposals identified in this study overlap with policy proposals common in the post-growth literature. Systematic reviews highlight UBI, WTR, and job-guarantee programs as among the most frequently discussed top-down policies in post-growth scholarship (N. Fitzpatrick et al., 2022). This convergence aligns with the findings of this research and underscores collaboration across academic communities. It also raises questions about the extent of current collaboration between eco-social and post-growth research fields and whether greater collaboration could help address resource constraints and avoid parallel lines of inquiry. Evidence of such cross-fertilization appears, for instance, in the program of the combined 18th International Society for Ecological Economics Conference and 11th International Degrowth Conference, which included sessions on welfare-state growth dependencies, social-ecological work, and post-growth social protection (ISEE-Degrowth 2025 Conference, 2025).

⁸⁴ (O’Neill et al., 2018; Vogel & Hickel, 2023)

⁸⁵ (Coote & Percy, 2020)

⁸⁶ See section “Qualitative Synthesis of Eco-Social Policy Proposals”.

More broadly, some scholars take an *optimistic view*. Koch (2020, p. 118) argues that eco-social policies could overcome growth imperatives if integrated into a comprehensive, coherent strategy. Hirvilammi (2020) further stresses that policymakers often lack the imaginative capacity to envision growth-independent welfare systems, being constrained by entrenched narratives of growth dependency. She argues that identifying mechanisms of dependence and articulating credible alternatives – such as the “virtuous circle of sustainable welfare” – could expand political feasibility. The virtuous circle integrates reinforcing social elements (e.g., equitable employment, sufficient consumption, stable tax bases, redistribution, and sustainable wellbeing) with environmental elements aligned with planetary boundaries (e.g., maintaining natural resource use within biocapacity, ensuring circular material flows, regenerating biodiversity, and adhering to carbon budgets) (Hirvilammi, 2020, p. 9).

Both the potential of eco-social policies to reduce growth dependencies and the importance of challenging growth-dependent policy imaginaries point to a greater likelihood of policy implementation. However, ultimately, the implementation of eco-social policies in democratic contexts hinges on *public support* and *coalition-building* within the eco-social policy domain (Bohnenberger, 2023, p. 333).

Summary

This chapter contributes to ongoing debates on the transformative potential, conceptualization, packages, and implementation of eco-social policies. It invites to further discuss the role of eco-social policies – being the instrument for achieving sustainable welfare. Building on identifying eco-social policy proposals in the research process and a critical engagement with dominant eco-social policy conceptualizations, the chapter aims to advance the research field by introducing a theory-of-change perspective on eco-social policies. This approach clarifies causal relationships by distinguishing between ecological and social objectives at the output, outcome, and impact levels. On this basis, the chapter proposes a typology differentiating strong eco-social policies – those combining ecological and social objectives at the output level – from weak eco-social policies, understood as either environmentally-extended social policies or socially-extended environmental policies. The discussion further argues for a shift away from singular flagship policies toward eco-social policy packages and highlights the importance of research on policy implementation – emphasizing political-economic constraints as a decisive factor requiring further research.

6. Conclusion

This thesis set out to critically engage with and contribute to the development of research on eco-social policy and sustainable welfare. It addressed the overarching research question: *Which eco-social policy proposals are discussed in contemporary academic literature within the sustainable welfare and eco-social policy research field?* Three sub-questions guided the analysis: (a) Which categories of eco-social policy proposals are most prominent? (b) Which individual proposals receive the most substantive attention? (c) Which ecological and social objectives are associated with these proposals and serve as the rationale for categorizing them as eco-social policy proposals?

Key Findings

The analysis generated several key findings: first, the analysis identifies five categories of eco-social policy proposals with sufficient research density: basic income policies, working time policies, basic service policies, income and wealth regulation policies, and labor-market policies. The final sample is dominated by the first three, while income and wealth regulation policies receive comparatively limited attention and labor-market-oriented proposals remain marginal.

Second, several proposals have emerged as focal points in the field. UBI, WTR, and UBS constitute the core proposals. Semi-core proposals include participation income, selected income and wealth regulation instruments (e.g., progressive taxation, income or wealth caps), and labor guarantees. Peripheral proposals – such as eco-social vouchers, transition income, working time redistribution instruments (e.g., paternity leave, job-sharing), and eco-social retraining or information policies – attract substantially less attention. The so-called “House of Eco-Social Policy Proposals” provides a visual backdrop of the contemporary research landscape.

Third, the objectives attributed to eco-social policies vary considerably across publications. Some studies present explicit causal pathways linking policies to ecological or social effects, while others rely on implicit or indirect mechanisms, especially regarding ecological effects. Social objectives range from broad notions of basic needs satisfaction to more specific aims such as reducing dependence on wage labor. Ecological objectives span concrete objectives of regenerative forms of work to more general commitments to respecting planetary boundaries.

Finally, the characteristics of the final sample were examined. From an initial pool of 824 publications identified through WoS and the EW database, the application of inclusion and exclusion criteria yielded 101 relevant publications. Due to resource constraints, this number was further narrowed down to 23 highly relevant publications. Most are published between 2022 and 2024, and approximately two-thirds appear in journals focused on social policy or sustainability. A large share is indexed in both databases.

Theoretical Implications and Future Research Avenues

This study advances the research field of eco-social policy and sustainable welfare in several ways: by mapping the prominence of different policy categories and singular policy proposals, it clarifies the current direction of scholarly debate and identifies under-researched areas – most notably eco-social labor-market policies. The findings also elucidate how proposals such as UBI, WTR, and UBS are framed as eco-social, highlighting divergent causal logics and degrees of conceptual explicitness.

The discussion contributes to debates on transformative potential, eco-social policy conceptualization, policy packages, and implementation. It invites further discussion on the role of eco-social policies as instruments for achieving sustainable welfare. Furthermore, building on the identification of eco-social policy proposals and a critical engagement with prevailing eco-social policy conceptualizations, a theory-of-change perspective on eco-social policies is introduced – seeking to foster the research field’s development. This perspective enhances analytical clarity by differentiating between ecological and social objectives across output, outcome, and impact levels. This framework underpins the proposed typology distinguishing strong eco-social policies – which integrate ecological and social objectives already at the output level – from weak eco-social policies, which manifest either as environmentally-extended social policies or as socially-extended environmental policies. The framework and typology both offer future research avenues – for instance by applying them for (a) systematic literature reviews on prominent eco-social policies such as UBI, WTR and UBS, or (b) eco-social policy evaluation in the field.

Furthermore, the findings point to the importance of shifting the analytical focus from individual flagship proposals to coherent eco-social policy packages. By drawing on established policy domains, such packages improve conceptual clarity and open up possibilities for policy combinations with enhanced transformative potential. The discussion also underlines the necessity for future research to move beyond policy design considerations and engage more systematically with implementation challenges. In particular, political–economic structures

constitute a central condition shaping the feasibility of eco-social policies and remain insufficiently explored in the existing literature.

Limitations

The SLR conducted in this thesis is subject to several methodological limitations that warrant explicit reflection. These limitations relate to the search strategy, the application of inclusion and exclusion criteria, and the composition and coding of the final sample:

The search strategy was intentionally selective. Terms such as “degrowth policies” and “just transition” were excluded to maintain a manageable scope and because preliminary testing indicated that their inclusion would produce an unfeasibly large number of results. Including “degrowth policies” risked biasing the sample toward post-growth variants of eco-social policy. Because the aim of this study was to specifically map the research field “eco-social policies and sustainable welfare”, it was methodologically appropriate to exclude the search term “just transition,” despite its conceptual proximity and partial overlap with eco-social policy debates.

Limitations also arise from the application of inclusion and exclusion criteria. Identifying “policy proposals” as “eco-social policy proposals” is inherently challenging – even more so in the context of mapping the landscape of different eco-social policy proposals and not only focusing on one proposal exclusively. Although SLRs aim to enhance reliability by importing quantitative standards into qualitative research, such standards cannot fully resolve the interpretive nature of determining whether publications meet criteria such as “focus of study.” This difficulty stems partly from conceptual heterogeneity: authors may label a policy “eco-social” despite it not fulfilling the definitional criteria employed in this thesis, necessitating additional content-based assessment. Further, peer-reviewed publications rarely state policy objectives with the clarity typical of policy documents. As a result, indicators such as policy expectations and observed policy effects were also used to infer policy objectives. This more generative approach, while necessary to achieve a sufficient number of eco-social policy proposals, reduces the reliability of the final sample and findings. These limitations were mitigated by extensive transparency in documenting search queries and eligibility criteria.

A potential researcher bias must also be acknowledged. On the one hand, given the author’s background in post-growth research, which also discuss policies such as UBI and UBS, there was a risk of inadvertently privileging such proposals during the sampling phase. This risk was minimized through strict adherence to the eligibility criteria. On the other hand, the selection of publications for the EW database may be subject to unconscious biases on the part of

contributing researchers, potentially affecting the database's representativeness. This risk was mitigated by complementing the EW database with the WoS and by applying transparent and predefined eligibility criteria throughout the sampling process.

Finally, limitations relate to the composition and coding of the final sample. The final sample count of 23 publications limits generalizability but was necessary given the scope of a master thesis. Future research could extend this work using larger samples and automated or semi-automated coding tools. Coding also included secondary findings because conceptual publications often do not clearly distinguish findings from theoretical argumentation. Although this approach was necessary given the nature of the field, it reduces uniformity of datasets, which negatively affects comparability. Moreover, no intercoder reliability check was possible due to the single-researcher design. Subsequent studies could improve reliability by incorporating multiple coders.

Closing Remarks

Despite these limitations, the study offers a substantial contribution to research on eco-social policy and sustainable welfare. It provides a first synthesis of eco-social policy proposals, critically interrogates prevailing conceptualizations, and proposes conceptual extensions that strengthen the field's analytical foundations. In doing so, it sharpens the instrument – *eco-social policy* – needed to advance a *social-ecological transformation* capable of ensuring needs satisfaction for all within planetary boundaries.

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Appendix A: The 2025 Update to the Planetary Boundaries

Figure 12: The 2025 Update to the Planetary Boundaries; reprinted from Stockholm Resilience Center (2025), Licensed under CC BY-NC-ND 3.0

Appendix B: Search String Overview

Web of Science: All collections

Range: 2021-01-01 to 2025-04-29

A -> eco-social policy ([link](#))

Topic: „eco-social polic*“

Range: 2021-01-01 to 2025-04-29

n = 70

B -> „eco-social pol & sus wel ([link](#))

Topic: „eco-social polic*“ OR "sustainable welfare"

n = 120

B1 -> eco-social pol, sus wel, environ. pol + soc. pol ([link](#))

Topic: "eco-social polic*“ OR "sustainable welfare" OR ("environmental polic*" AND "social polic*")

n= 146

-> testing: inclusion criteria applied for first 50 results (descending relevance):

- high relevance: 2
- medium relevance: 6
- low relevance: 2

-> Possibility of including "sufficiency policy," as this pursues a similar goal to eco-social policies and increases n somewhat.

B2 -> eco-social pol, sus wel, environ. pol + soc. pol, sufficiency pol ([link](#))

Topic: "eco-social polic*“ OR "sustainable welfare" OR ("environmental polic*" AND "social polic*") OR "sufficiency polic*" OR "just transition"

n = 167

-> very fitting and appropriate n

-> testing with addition of “just transition” due to the socially-extended environmental policies / eco-social policies being linked to just transition

B3 -> eco-social pol, sus wel, environ. pol + soc. pol, sufficiency pol + just transi. ([link](#))

Topic: "eco-social polic*" OR "sustainable welfare" OR ("environmental polic*" AND "social polic*") OR "sufficiency polic*" OR "just transition*"

n=1,241

-> too much

C -> environment plus social policy ([link](#))

Topic: ("climate" OR "sustainab*" OR "environment*" OR "decarbon*" OR "socio-ecolog*" OR "eco-social*" OR "transformation" OR "transition" OR "biodiversity" OR "green") AND "social policy"

n=765

-> too much

C1 -> environment plus social policy

("climate" OR "sustainab*" OR "environment*" OR "decarbon*" OR "socio-ecolog*" OR "eco-social*" OR "transformation" OR "transition" OR "biodiversity" OR "green" OR "ecolog*" OR "planetary boundar*") AND "social policy"

n=786

-> too much

D -> social plus environmental policy ([link](#))

Topic: ("welfare state" OR "social policy" OR "eco-socio*" OR "welfare benefits" OR "job" OR "employment" OR "poverty" OR "wealth" OR "justice") AND "environmental policy"

n= 286

D1 -> social plus environmental policy

Topic: ("welfare" OR "social" OR "eco-socio*" OR "job" OR "employment" OR "poverty" OR "wealth" OR "justice" OR "wellbeing" OR "well-being" OR "needs" OR "distribution*") AND "environmental policy"

n=1,444

-> too much

-> The search terms "welfare" and "social" push the number up.

E1 -> Kombination aus C & D ([link](#))

Topic: (("climate" OR "sustainab*" OR "environment*" OR "decarbon*" OR "socio-ecolog*" OR "eco-social*" OR "transformation" OR "transition" OR "biodiversity" OR "green") AND "social policy") OR (("welfare state" OR "social policy" OR "eco-socio*" OR "welfare benefits" OR "job" OR "employment" OR "poverty" OR "wealth" OR "justice") AND "environmental policy")

n=1,034

-> too much

E2 -> Kombination aus C & D & A ([link](#))

Topic: (("climate" OR "sustainab*" OR "environment*" OR "decarbon*" OR "socio-ecolog*" OR "eco-social*" OR "transformation" OR "transition" OR "biodiversity" OR "green") AND "social policy") OR (("welfare state" OR "social policy" OR "eco-socio*" OR "welfare benefits" OR "job" OR "employment" OR "poverty" OR "wealth" OR "justice") AND "environmental policy") OR „eco-social polic*“ OR "sustainable welfare"

n=1,058

-> too much

-> quick scan of No. 1-50 and No. 1001-1058 (descending relevance)

- No. 1-50: 18 relevant (4 highly relevant; 8 moderate relevant; 6 low relevant)
- No. 101-151: 2 relevant (1 moderate, 1 low)
- No. 1001-1058: 1 relevant (1 highly)

-> dissatisfied because after the first 100 or so publications, the subsequent publications no longer have anything to do with the topic and are therefore irrelevant.

-> conclusion: input-output ratio from roughly 100 not ideal; too much irrelevant publications; include „sustainable welfare“ to increase input-output-ratio while keeping sufficient n

E3 -> Kombination aus C & D & A + sus welf ([link](#))

Topic: (("climate" OR "sustainab*" OR "environment*" OR "decarbon*" OR "socio-ecolog*" OR "eco-social*" OR "transformation" OR "transition" OR "biodiversity" OR "green") AND "social policy") OR (("welfare state" OR "social policy" OR "eco-socio*" OR "welfare benefits" OR "job" OR "employment" OR "poverty" OR "wealth" OR "justice") AND "environmental policy") OR „eco-social polic*“ OR "sustainable welfare"

n = 1,103

-> too much

F -> polic* & environment & social ([link](#))

Topic: "polic*" AND ("climate" OR "sustainab*" OR "environment*" OR "decarbon*" OR "socio-ecolog*" OR "eco-social*" OR "transformation" OR "transition" OR "biodiversity" OR "green") AND ("welfare state" OR "social policy" OR "eco-socio*" OR "welfare benefits" OR "job" OR "employment" OR "poverty" OR "wealth" OR "justice")

n=20,157

-> search query terms based of Bohnenberger (2023)

-> too much

G -> polic* & environ & social ([link](#))

Topic: "polic*" AND ("climate" OR "sustainab*" OR "environment*" OR "decarbon*" OR "socio-ecolog*" OR "eco-social*" OR "transformation" OR "transition" OR "biodiversity" OR "green" OR "ecolog*" OR "planetary boundar*") AND ("welfare" OR "social" OR "eco-socio*" OR "job" OR "employment" OR "poverty" OR "wealth" OR "justice" OR "wellbeing" OR "well-being" OR "needs")

n= 74,875

-> too much

H -> Keyword polic* & Topic environ. & social ([link](#))

Keyword: "polic*" AND Topic: "climate" OR "sustainab*" OR "environment*" OR "decarbon*" OR "socio-ecolog*" OR "eco-social*" OR "transformation" OR "transition" OR "biodiversity" OR "green" OR "ecolog*" OR "planetary boundar*" AND "welfare" OR "social" OR "eco-socio*" OR "job" OR "employment" OR "poverty" OR "wealth" OR "justice" OR "wellbeing" OR "well-being" OR "needs"

n= 18,756

-> too much

I -> Keywords polic* & Topic environ. & social

Keywords: "polic*" AND Topic: "climate" OR "sustainab*" OR "environment*" OR "decarbon*" OR "socio-ecolog*" OR "eco-social*" OR "transformation" OR "transition" OR "biodiversity" OR "green" OR "ecolog*" OR "planetary boundar*" AND "welfare" OR "social" OR "eco-socio*" OR "job" OR "employment" OR "poverty" OR "wealth" OR "justice" OR "wellbeing" OR "well-being" OR "needs" OR "distribution*"

n= 13,176

-> too much

Appendix C: MAXQDA Coding Snippet

Figure 13: MAXQDA Coding Snippet

Appendix D: All Databases

The list of all samples is available upon request from the author.